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Charge reconstruction in magnetic heterostructures

A real space dynamical mean-field approach

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1. Introduction to the physical problem

Strongly correlated electron systems display many interesting phenomena. Among them are the Mott metal-insulator transition [1,2], high-temperature superconductivity, and colossal electroresistance [3] and colossal magnetoresistance [4], where small electric or magnetic field changes result in large changes in the electric resistivity. Often this class of materials has several competing states resulting in complex phase diagrams. Thus, small perturbations can lead to drastic changes of the properties. This high sensitivity and the resulting large responses are interesting, as they can be employed for technical applications. [5]

The modeling of physical properties of these materials faces, however, a strong conceptual barrier, as the properties cannot be explained using standard methods, based on a single particle picture. The physics is essentially many-body; concepts such as band theory are expected to fail [6].

To build devices out of these interesting materials, the strongly correlated electron systems typically need to be interfaced, either with conventional materials or with other strongly correlated materials. Thus, for technical applications, the knowledge of the bulk properties is not sufficient. To determine the properties of such devices, we need to study the interface properties of strongly correlated electron systems. The question arises how inhomogeneities and spatial confinement affect quantum correlations. This problem combines the fields of strong electron correlation with nanotechnology. [7]

The properties of such interfaces and heterostructures may drastically differ from the bulk system. A prominent example is the appearance of a metallic interface between two different insulators [8–10]. To describe such phenomena it is essential to include electronic charge reconstruction. If the Fermi levels of the constituents do not match, electrons diffuse from one constituent to the other, until a stationary equilibrium is achieved. Thus, it is not sufficient to include only local interactions, long-ranged interactions also have to be taken into account.

Due to the complexity of the problem of strong electronic correlations, we study model Hamiltonians. We use a single-band Hubbard Hamiltonian [11], as it is the simplest model that can yield a metallic and a Mott insulating phase [12]. In spite of its formal simplicity, the Hubbard model still is not solved. We extend it by long-ranged Coulomb interactions to allow for charge reconstruction. We treat the long-ranged interaction on a mean-field level.

In this thesis we will focus on half-metallic layers sandwiched between metallic leads. A half-metal is a material, where one spin channel is insulating while the other spin channel remains metallic [13,14]. This class of materials has gained much interest, due to its applicability for spin electronics. To build devices, the spin polarization of the conductivity is of central interest, notably the conductivity through heterostructures containing a half-metal is relevant. We will focus on a model that consists of a single half-metallic layer sandwiched between non-magnetic metallic layers. We consider strong electronic interaction for the half-metallic layer, treated according to [15], and include long-ranged interaction due to charge reconstruction on a mean-field level according to [7].

Outline of the thesis. Section 2 introduces the necessary methods to treat correlated heterostructures. We explain how to use dynamical mean-field theory to treat strong local electron correlations in our heterostructure, and include long-ranged interactions on a mean-field level by solving the classical Poisson equation for the electrostatic potential. In section 3 we show the results for the heterostructure with a single interacting half-metallic layer in the center, the surrounding layers are metallic and non-magnetic. We investigate the one-particle quantities, the occupation and the spectral function, and analyze their dependence on the local and the long-ranged interaction. Section 4 gives an outlook on the transmission in this setup.

2. Strong electronic correlation in heterostructures

We use a single-band Hubbard model to describe correlated heterostructures. The system Hamiltonian is given by:

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{i,\sigma} \epsilon_i \hat{n}_{i\sigma} + \sum_{ij,\sigma} t_{ij} \hat{c}_{i\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{j\sigma} + \sum_i U_i \hat{n}_{i\uparrow} \hat{n}_{i\downarrow}. \quad (2.1)$$

Here $\hat{c}_{i\sigma}^\dagger$ and $\hat{c}_{i\sigma}$ are the fermionic creation and annihilation operators at site i with spin σ . We denote the number operator at site i with $\hat{n}_{i\sigma} = \hat{c}_{i\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{i\sigma}$. Furthermore, the parameter ϵ_i is the on-site energy, t_{ij} are the hopping matrix elements, and U_i is the Hubbard interaction. The hopping matrix is Hermitian $t_{ij} = t_{ji}^*$.

While there exists a solution in one-dimensional systems [16], we cannot solve this problem in general in higher dimensions. The dynamical mean-field theory (DMFT) [17, 18], however, provides a non-perturbative approach, which can be applied for any range of parameters and is exact in the limit of infinite coordination number. It is furthermore exact for both limits, the non-interacting limit $U_i = 0$ and the atomic limit $t_{ij} = 0$. In section 2.1 we first introduce DMFT for a homogeneous system, where all sites are equivalent. In section 2.2 we derive an algorithm for layered heterostructures based on the DMFT for homogeneous systems. In section 2.3 we extend the Hubbard Hamiltonian eq. (2.1) with a long-ranged Coulomb interaction, which we treat on a mean-field level. The combined scheme of section 2.2 and section 2.3 is then presented in section 2.4.

2.1. Dynamical mean-field theory (DMFT)

In static mean-field theories the lattice problem is approximated by an effective single site problem. The site is only coupled to an effective parameter, which is determined by the rest of the lattice. Dynamical mean-field theory, on the other hand, is a self-consistent mapping of the lattice problem onto an impurity problem. An impurity model couples, in our case, a single site to a large reservoir of non-interacting electrons. Thus, it couples a site to a time or frequency dependent *effective bath*, instead of a static parameter. This way, *local* time-dependent fluctuations can be taken into account.

We will use the so-called *cavity method*, following the derivations of [17–21]. The general idea of this method is the following: one interacting lattice site is selected and singled out, it is mapped onto an interacting impurity embedded in a non-interacting bath. The remaining sites are integrated out and determine the bath. We solve the impurity problem and use its self-energy for the lattice site. For now, we assume a translational invariant system, thus we can use the impurity self-energy for all lattice sites. This mapping procedure is repeated until self-consistency is achieved.

Figure 2.1: Basic concept of dynamical mean-field theory (DMFT). The lattice problem is substituted by an effective impurity model. One interacting lattice site will be picked, the rest of the lattice is treated as a non-interacting bath. Electrons can hop between the interacting site and the bath, thus local correlations are included. This effective bath is self-consistently determined, the self-energy $\Sigma(i\omega_n)$ obtained from the impurity problem is used for the lattice.

We work in the field integral representation. For the reader not familiar with it, we introduce the formalism and nomenclature in appendix A. The grand canonical partition function of the lattice Hamiltonian eq. (2.1) reads

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{c}, c] e^{-S_{\text{lat}}[\bar{c}, c]} \quad (2.2)$$

$$S_{\text{lat}}[\bar{c}, c] = \int_0^\beta d\tau \left(\sum_{ij\sigma} \bar{c}_{i\sigma} [(\partial_\tau - \mu_i + \epsilon_i)\delta_{ij} + t_{ij}] c_{j\sigma} + \sum_i U_i n_{i\uparrow} n_{i\downarrow} \right). \quad (2.3)$$

$c_{i\sigma}$ and $\bar{c}_{i\sigma}$ are Grassmann fields, and $n_{i\sigma} := \bar{c}_{i\sigma} c_{i\sigma}$.¹ With c and \bar{c} we denote the set of all Grassmann fields $c = \{c_{i\sigma}\}$ and $\bar{c} = \{\bar{c}_{i\sigma}\}$.

¹The Grassmann fields are always functions of the imaginary time τ unless specified differently. We do not explicitly note this dependency if all quantities depend on the same τ .

We select an arbitrary site $i = \circ$ and single it out by tracing out all other sites

$$\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_{eff}} e^{-S_{eff}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}]} := \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \int \prod_{i \neq \circ, \sigma} \mathcal{D}[\bar{c}_{i\sigma}, c_{i\sigma}] e^{-S_{lat}}. \quad (2.4)$$

The action $S_{eff}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}]$ defines the effective single site problem, which needs to be solved. By definition (2.4), the expectation value with respect to the effective action of *local* quantities $\mathcal{O}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}]$ is the same as the expectation value in the lattice system $\langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_{S_{eff}} \equiv \langle \mathcal{O} \rangle_S$.

2.1.1. Action in the non-interacting limit

We first consider the non-interacting case $U_i = 0$ and show how to generalize the approach to interacting systems $U_i \neq 0$ in the next section 2.1.2. Now we explicitly derive the effective action S_{eff} for the site \circ . We split the lattice action eq. (2.3) into three parts

$$S^{(\circ)} = \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{ij \neq \circ, \sigma} \bar{c}_{i\sigma} [(\partial_\tau - \mu_i + \epsilon_i) \delta_{ij} + t_{ij}] c_{j\sigma} \quad (2.5)$$

$$S_\circ = \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_\sigma \bar{c}_{\circ\sigma} (\partial_\tau - \mu_\circ + \epsilon_\circ) c_{\circ\sigma} \quad (2.6)$$

$$\Delta S = \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{i \neq \circ, \sigma} (\bar{c}_{i\sigma} t_{i\circ} c_{\circ\sigma} + \bar{c}_{\circ\sigma} t_{\circ i} c_{i\sigma}). \quad (2.7)$$

$S^{(\circ)}$ is the action of the lattice with a cavity, S_\circ the part containing only variables of the site \circ , and ΔS the hopping between the site \circ and the lattice with the cavity. In the following, the phrase cavity quantity designates a quantity of the lattice with a cavity. As the action S_\circ of the site \circ is independent of all other sites, we can pull S_\circ out of the integrations:

$$\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_{eff}} e^{-S_{eff}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}]} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} e^{-S_\circ} \int \prod_{i \neq \circ, \sigma} \mathcal{D}[\bar{c}_{i\sigma}, c_{i\sigma}] e^{-S^{(\circ)}} e^{-\Delta S}. \quad (2.8)$$

We identify the weighted integral on the right-hand side as the average over the cavity system $\langle \cdot \rangle_{S^{(\circ)}}$ and write

$$\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_{eff}} e^{-S_{eff}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}]} = \frac{\mathcal{Z}^{(\circ)}}{\mathcal{Z}} e^{-S_\circ} \langle e^{-\Delta S} \rangle_{S^{(\circ)}}, \quad (2.9)$$

with the cavity partition function $Z^{(\circ)}$ corresponding to $\langle \cdot \rangle_{S^{(\circ)}}$. In the non-interacting case, the cavity action $S^{(\circ)}$ and thus the whole integrand is quadratic in the Grassmann fields; we can evaluate the integral. In the frequency representation the Gaussian integral (compare eq. (A.31)) yields

$$\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_{eff}} e^{-S_{eff}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma n}, c_{\circ\sigma n}]} = \frac{\det(G_{0ij}^{(\circ)})}{\mathcal{Z}} e^{-S_{\circ}} \exp\left(-\sum_{\{i\omega_n\}} \sum_{ij \neq \circ, \sigma} \bar{c}_{\circ\sigma n} t_{oi} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\circ} c_{\circ\sigma n}\right), \quad (2.10)$$

with the non-interacting cavity Green's function $G_{0ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) = -\langle c_{i\sigma n} \bar{c}_{j\sigma n} \rangle_{S^{(\circ)}}$, $i, j \neq \circ$ and $c_{i\sigma n} \equiv c_{i\sigma}(i\omega_n)$. The constant $\ln(\det(G_{0ij}^{(\circ)})\mathcal{Z}_{eff}/\mathcal{Z})$ in the effective action has no physical meaning, so we drop it and get

$$\begin{aligned} S_{eff}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma n}, c_{\circ\sigma n}] &= S_{\circ} + \sum_{\{i\omega_n\}} \sum_{ij \neq \circ, \sigma} \bar{c}_{\circ\sigma n} t_{oi} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\circ} c_{\circ\sigma n} \\ &= \sum_{\{i\omega_n\}} \sum_{\sigma} \bar{c}_{\circ\sigma n} \left(-i\omega_n - \mu_{\circ} + \epsilon_{\circ} + \sum_{ij \neq \circ} t_{oi} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\circ} \right) c_{\circ\sigma n}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

In the non-interacting case we can directly solve the effective problem. However, in the interacting case it will be helpful to identify it with another model, the *single-impurity Anderson model* (SIAM), as numerical solvers are available for it.

Equivalence with the action of a non-interacting SIAM. In the following we will see, that the effective action eq. (2.11) is formally identical to the non-interacting SIAM. The Hamiltonian of the non-interacting SIAM is given

$$\hat{H}_{imp} = \sum_{\sigma} \epsilon \hat{c}_{\sigma}^{\dagger} \hat{c}_{\sigma} + \sum_{k, \sigma} \left(V_k \hat{a}_{k\sigma}^{\dagger} \hat{c}_{\sigma} + H.c. \right) + \sum_{k, \sigma} \epsilon_k \hat{a}_{k\sigma}^{\dagger} \hat{a}_{k\sigma}. \quad (2.12)$$

$\hat{a}_{k\sigma}^{\dagger}$ ($\hat{a}_{k\sigma}$) are the fermionic creation (annihilation) operators of the non-interacting bath, and $\hat{c}_{\sigma}^{\dagger}$ (\hat{c}_{σ}) of the impurity site. In the action representation the bath operators can readily be integrated out. This yields the action of the non-interacting impurity

$$S_{imp}[\bar{c}_{\sigma}, c_{\sigma}] = -\sum_{\{i\omega_n\}} \sum_{\sigma} \bar{c}_{\sigma n} G_{0imp}^{-1}(i\omega_n) c_{\sigma n} \quad (2.13)$$

with the non-interacting impurity Green's function

$$G_{0imp}(i\omega_n) =: -\langle c_{\sigma} \bar{c}_{\sigma} \rangle_{S_{imp}} = \left(i\omega_n + \mu - \epsilon - \Delta(i\omega_n) \right)^{-1}, \quad \Delta(i\omega_n) = \sum_k \frac{|V_k|^2}{i\omega_n - \epsilon_k}. \quad (2.14)$$

We introduced the hybridization function $\Delta(i\omega_n)$. It characterizes the non-interacting bath of the SIAM, as the full information of the bath is contained in this function.

The impurity action can be constructed by giving the non-interacting impurity Green's function $S_{\text{imp}}[G_{0\text{imp}}]$. We compare the effective action eq. (2.11) with the impurity action eq. (2.13). We identify that for the choice

$$G_{0\text{imp}}^{-1} = i\omega_n + \mu_\circ - \epsilon_\circ - \sum_{ij} t_{\circ i} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\circ} =: \mathcal{G}_0^{-1}(i\omega_n) \quad (2.15)$$

the actions are identical $S_{\text{eff}}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}] = S_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_0; \bar{c}_\sigma, c_\sigma]$. Thus, we interpret the effective problem S_{eff} as an impurity problem $S_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_0]$ which is fully specified by \mathcal{G}_0 . We call \mathcal{G}_0 *Weiss function* or *effective bath*. Instead of using the non-interacting impurity Green's function, we can specify the impurity action by the hybridization function $S_{\text{eff}}[\Delta]$ and fix ϵ and μ to the corresponding parameters of the lattice model. Equivalent to eq. (2.15) we identify that for the choice

$$\Delta(i\omega_n) = \sum_{ij} t_{\circ i} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\circ} \quad (2.16)$$

the effective and the impurity action are identical $S_{\text{eff}}[\bar{c}_{\circ\sigma}, c_{\circ\sigma}] = S_{\text{imp}}[\Delta; \bar{c}_\sigma, c_\sigma]$.

To briefly summarize the section up this point: we mapped the lattice problem onto the SIAM. We picked one lattice site \circ and singled it out. The rest of the lattice, the cavity lattice, is treated as the effective *non-interacting* bath of the SIAM.

The mapping of the lattice problem onto the impurity problem still contains the cavity Green's function. So far we just rephrased the lattice problem with an unknown quantity, the cavity Green's function. We still need to discuss this new quantity $G_{ij}^{(\circ)}$. For any lattice the equation

$$G_{0ij}^{(\circ)} \equiv G_{0ij} - \frac{G_{0i\circ} G_{0\circ j}}{G_{0\circ\circ}} \quad (2.17)$$

links the cavity and the lattice non-interacting Green's function. This relation can be motivated using the interpretation of the Green's function as a propagator: in addition to the paths in the cavity Green's function $G_0^{(\circ)}$, the lattice Green's functions G_0 contains all possible paths going through the site \circ . A derivation is given in appendix B, see eq. (B.7). After further simplifications we get eq. (B.12):

$$\sum_{ij} t_{\circ i} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)} t_{j\circ} = i\omega_n + \mu_\circ - \epsilon_\circ - G_{0\circ\circ}^{-1}. \quad (2.18)$$

In the non-interacting case, the effective bath eq. (2.15) takes with this relation the trivial form

$$\mathcal{G}_0 \equiv G_{0\circ\circ} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \frac{1}{i\omega_n + \mu_\circ - \epsilon_\circ - \epsilon_k}. \quad (2.19)$$

Plugging eq. (2.18) into the hybridization function eq. (2.16), we can also express the hybridization function in terms of the local lattice Green's function

$$\Delta[G_{0\circ\circ}] = i\omega_n + \mu_\circ - \epsilon_\circ - G_{0\circ\circ}^{-1}. \quad (2.20)$$

The effective bath \mathcal{G}_0 and the hybridization function Δ do not depend on any non-local Green's functions $G_{0i\sigma}$, thus they can be calculated using the effective action eq. (2.4). Solving the impurity problem $S_{\text{imp}}[G_{0\text{imp}}]$ for the effective bath \mathcal{G}_0 yields again the effective bath itself as local Green's function $G_{0o\sigma} \equiv G_{0\text{imp}} = \mathcal{G}_0$. The non-interacting limit is a pathological limit, as we replaced the already non-interacting cavity lattice by a non-interacting bath. It is still instructive as we show in the next section how to generalize the scheme to interacting systems in the limit of infinite coordination number.

2.1.2. Derivation of the DMFT equations

We consider now an interacting system and go through the same steps as in section 2.1.1. Again we split the lattice action S_{lat} into the three parts

$$S^{(o)} = \int_0^\beta d\tau \left(\sum_{ij \neq o, \sigma} \bar{c}_{i\sigma} [(\partial_\tau - \mu_i + \epsilon_i) \delta_{ij} + t_{ij}] c_{j\sigma} + \sum_{i \neq o} U_i n_{i\uparrow} n_{i\downarrow} \right) \quad (2.21)$$

$$S_o = \int_0^\beta d\tau \left(\sum_\sigma \bar{c}_{o\sigma} (\partial_\tau - \mu_o + \epsilon_o) c_{o\sigma} + U_o n_{o\uparrow} n_{o\downarrow} \right) \quad (2.22)$$

$$\Delta S = \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{i \neq o, \sigma} (\bar{c}_{i\sigma} t_{io} c_{o\sigma} + \bar{c}_{o\sigma} t_{oi} c_{i\sigma}). \quad (2.23)$$

Exactly as in the non-interacting system eq. (2.9) we get

$$\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_{\text{eff}}} e^{-S_{\text{eff}}[\bar{c}_{o\sigma}, c_{o\sigma}]} = \frac{\mathcal{Z}^{(o)}}{\mathcal{Z}} e^{-S_o} \langle e^{-\Delta S} \rangle_{S^{(o)}}, \quad (2.24)$$

by pulling S_o out of the integral for the effective action eq. (2.4), and writing the integral as average over the cavity system. In the interacting case however, we cannot evaluate the cavity average $\langle \cdot \rangle_{S^{(o)}}$ as the cavity action $S^{(o)}$ is not quadratic in the Grassmann fields.

We can still express the average in terms of interacting cavity Green's functions. The average $\langle e^{-\Delta S} \rangle_{S^{(o)}}$ is the generating functional [22, 23] of the cavity Green's functions. We can identify $\eta_{i\sigma} \equiv t_{io} c_{o\sigma}$ and $\bar{\eta}_{i\sigma} \equiv \bar{c}_{o\sigma} t_{oi}$ as the source terms:

$$e^{-S_{\text{eff}}[\{\eta_{i\sigma}\}, \{\bar{\eta}_{i\sigma}\}]} = \frac{\mathcal{Z}_{\text{eff}} \mathcal{Z}^{(o)}}{\mathcal{Z}} e^{-S_o} \left\langle e^{-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{i \neq o, \sigma} (\bar{c}_{i\sigma} \eta_{i\sigma} + \bar{\eta}_{i\sigma} c_{i\sigma})} \right\rangle_{S^{(o)}}. \quad (2.25)$$

Differentiation with respect to the sources $\eta_{i\sigma}$ and $\bar{\eta}_{i\sigma}$ generates the Grassmann fields $\bar{c}_{i\sigma}$ and $c_{i\sigma}$ inside of the cavity average $\langle \cdot \rangle_{S^{(o)}}$. Consequently, the n -particle cavity Green's functions can be written as

$$(-1)^{n+1} G_{i_1 \dots i_n; j_1 \dots j_n}^{(o)} \propto \frac{\delta^{2n}}{\delta \bar{\eta}_{i_1}(\tau_1) \dots \delta \bar{\eta}_{i_n}(\tau_n) \delta \eta_{j_1}(\tau'_1) \dots \delta \eta_{j_n}(\tau'_n)} e^{-S_{eff}[\{\eta_{i\sigma}\}, \{\bar{\eta}_{i\sigma}\}]} \Big|_{\eta, \bar{\eta}=0}, \quad (2.26)$$

where we use the notation $G_{i_1 \dots i_n; j_1 \dots j_n}^{(o)} = -\langle c_{i_1}(\tau_1) \dots c_{i_n}(\tau_n) \bar{c}_{j_1}(\tau'_1) \dots \bar{c}_{j_n}(\tau'_n) \rangle_{S^{(o)}}$. We suppress the σ -indices. Grassmann numbers and derivatives anticommute, thus the factor $(-1)^n$ arises as we need to move the derivative $\frac{\delta}{\delta \eta}$ past \bar{c} to act on the source η . We can eliminate the sign by changing the order of the derivatives, first differentiating with respect to $\bar{\eta}$ and then with respect to η . The effective action S_{eff} is the logarithm of the generating functional eq. (2.25). Thus, we identify

$$-S_{eff}[\{\eta_{i\sigma}\}, \{\bar{\eta}_{i\sigma}\}] \propto \ln \left(\langle e^{-\Delta S} \rangle_{S^{(o)}} \right) \quad (2.27)$$

as the generating functional for *connected* Green's functions [23]

$$G_{c_{i_1 \dots i_n; j_1 \dots j_n}}^{(o)} = \frac{\delta^{2n}}{\delta \eta_{j_i}(\tau'_1) \dots \delta \eta_{j_n}(\tau'_n) \delta \bar{\eta}_{i_1}(\tau_1) \dots \delta \bar{\eta}_{i_n}(\tau_n)} S_{eff} \Big|_{\eta, \bar{\eta}=0}. \quad (2.28)$$

Averages with an unbalanced number of c and \bar{c} vanish for our action eq. (2.3), thus we can rewrite the effective action in terms of connected Green's functions

$$S_{eff} = -\ln \left(\frac{\mathcal{Z}_{eff} \mathcal{Z}^{(o)}}{\mathcal{Z}} \right) + S_o + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum'_{i_1 \dots j_n} \int d\tau_1 \dots \int d\tau'_n \bar{\eta}_{i_1} \dots \bar{\eta}_{i_n} \eta_{j_1} \dots \eta_{j_n} G_{c_{i_1 \dots i_n; j_1 \dots j_n}}^{(o)}. \quad (2.29)$$

The prime at the sum denotes ordered sums ($i_1 \geq i_2 \geq \dots; j_1 \geq j_2 \geq \dots$), else we would get an additional factor $1/(n!)^2$ accounting for permutations. This can be verified by comparing the derivatives of both sides. The difference compared to the non-interacting case eq. (2.11) is, that we have to consider all n -particle connected Green's functions in the interacting case, not only the 1-particle Green's function.²

In the limit of infinite coordination number $Z \rightarrow \infty$ this expression simplifies considerably. To arrive at a non-trivial limit the hopping elements t_{ij} need to be scaled $t_{ij} \rightarrow t_{ij}/Z^{\|i-j\|/2}$ [24], where $\|i-j\|$ is the 1-norm or Manhattan distance. Only the

²In the non-interacting case all higher order connected Green's functions vanish, as the non-interacting Green's functions factorize, see eq. (A.32). So this limit is consistent with the non-interacting case of section 2.1.1.

one particle Green's function³ survives and all higher order connected Green's functions vanish in the limit $Z \rightarrow \infty$ [17, 25]. In imaginary time representation we write

$$S_{eff}[c_{\sigma\sigma}, \bar{c}_{\sigma\sigma}] = \int_0^\beta d\tau \left(\sum_\sigma \bar{c}_{\sigma\sigma}(\tau) (\partial_\tau - \mu_\sigma + \epsilon_\sigma) c_{\sigma\sigma}(\tau) + U_\sigma n_{\sigma\uparrow}(\tau) n_{\sigma\downarrow}(\tau) \right) + \int_0^\beta d\tau \int_0^\beta d\tau' \sum_{ij \neq \sigma} t_{\sigma i} \bar{c}_{\sigma\sigma}(\tau) G_{ij}^{(\circ)}(\tau - \tau') t_{i\sigma} c_{\sigma\sigma}(\tau'). \quad (2.30)$$

This has the form of the effective action eq. (2.11) in the non-interacting case, with the addition of the interaction term.

Equivalence with the action of an interacting SIAM. The action of the SIAM is

$$S_{\text{imp}}[\bar{c}_\sigma, c_\sigma] = - \int_0^\beta d\tau \int_0^\beta d\tau' \sum_\sigma \bar{c}_\sigma(\tau) G_{0\text{imp}}^{-1}(\tau - \tau') c_\sigma(\tau) + U \int_0^\beta d\tau n_\uparrow(\tau) n_\downarrow(\tau). \quad (2.31)$$

The comparison of eq. (2.31) with the effective action eq. (2.30) yields the formally identical relations for \mathcal{G}_0 and Δ like the non-interacting case eq. (2.15) and eq. (2.16). The only difference is in the interacting case is, that the interacting cavity Green's function $G^{(\circ)}$ enters instead of the non-interacting cavity Green's function $G_0^{(\circ)}$. We identify, that for the following choice of the non-interacting impurity Green's function

$$G_{0\text{imp}}^{-1} = i\omega_n + \mu - \epsilon_\sigma - \sum_{ij} t_{\sigma i} G_{ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\sigma} =: \mathcal{G}_0^{-1} \quad (2.32)$$

the impurity action is identical to the effective action $S_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_0; c_\sigma, \bar{c}_\sigma] = S_{eff}[c_{\sigma\sigma}, \bar{c}_{\sigma\sigma}]$. Equivalently, we can describe the impurity action by the hybridization function $S_{\text{imp}}[\Delta]$. We identify that for

$$\Delta(i\omega_n) = \sum_{ij} t_{\sigma i} G_{ij}^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n) t_{j\sigma} \quad (2.33)$$

the effective and the impurity action are identical.

Again the next step is to establish a connection between the cavity Green's $G_{ij}^{(\circ)}$ function and the full lattice Green's function G_{ij} . In the limit of infinite coordination number, the self-energy is local $\Sigma_{ij}(i\omega_n) = \Sigma_i(i\omega_n) \delta_{ij}$ [26], and eq. (2.17) can be generalized to the interacting case

$$G_{ij}^{(\circ)} = G_{ij} - \frac{G_{i\sigma} G_{\sigma j}}{G_{\sigma\sigma}}, \quad (2.34)$$

³The one-particle Green's function G_{ij} and connected one $G_{c\ ij}$ are identical, thus we can drop the index c .

as discussed in appendix B, see eq. (B.16). We plug this relation into the effective bath and the hybridization function eqs. (2.32) and (2.33). For a *homogeneous* system all lattice sites are equivalent and thus $\Sigma_i(i\omega_n) = \Sigma(i\omega_n)$. We get after further simplifications⁴ the effective bath

$$\mathcal{G}_0^{-1} = \Sigma(i\omega_n) + G_{\text{oo}}^{-1} = \Sigma(i\omega_n) + \left(\int d\epsilon \frac{\rho(\epsilon)}{i\omega_n + \mu - \epsilon - \Sigma(i\omega_n) - \epsilon} \right)^{-1}, \quad (2.35)$$

and the hybridization function

$$\Delta(i\omega_n) = i\omega_n + \mu - \epsilon - \Sigma(i\omega_n) - G_{\text{oo}}^{-1}. \quad (2.36)$$

We replaced the k -sum in eq. (2.35) by the integral over the *non-interacting density of states* (DOS) $\rho(\epsilon) := \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \delta(\epsilon - \epsilon_k)$; we see that in the limit of infinite coordination number the k -dependency is absorbed into the DOS. In the limit of infinite coordination number the self-energy is k -independent, thus it carries no ϵ -argument after the substitution $\frac{1}{N} \sum_k \rightarrow \int d\epsilon \rho(\epsilon)$; we can write

$$G_{\text{oo}}(i\omega_n) = \int d\epsilon \frac{\rho(\epsilon)}{i\omega_n + \mu - \epsilon - \Sigma(i\omega_n) - \epsilon} = G_{0\text{oo}}(i\omega_n - \Sigma(i\omega_n)). \quad (2.37)$$

If we know the analytic expression for the non-interacting Green's function, we do not need to perform the integration. Equation (2.35) provides a way to self-consistently calculate the local Green's function $G_{\text{oo}} = G_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_0]$ by solving the SIAM $G_{\text{imp}}[G_{0\text{imp}}]$. An explicit scheme is given in algorithm 1.

```

Σ(iωn) = Σinitial(iωn)
repeat
    Goo(iωn) := ∫ dε  $\frac{\rho(\epsilon)}{i\omega_n + \mu - \epsilon - \Sigma(i\omega_n) - \epsilon}$ 
    G0-1(iωn) := Goo-1(iωn) + Σ(iωn)
    solve impurity problem Gimp[G0]
    Σ(iωn) := G0-1(iωn) - Gimp-1(iωn)
until self-consistency
    
```

Algorithm 1: Self-consistent DMFT equations.

We discuss two special cases for *finite* coordination number. In this case DMFT also yields the exact result for the non-interacting limit $U = 0$ and the atomic limit $t_{ij} = 0$. For $U = 0$ the solution for the impurity model is $G_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_0] = \mathcal{G}_0$. Thus, algorithm 1 correctly yields $\Sigma = \mathcal{G}_0^{-1} - G_{\text{imp}}^{-1} = 0$ and $G_{\text{loc}} = G_{0\text{loc}}$. For $t_{ij} = 0$ the DOS reduces to a delta-function $\rho(\epsilon) = \delta(\epsilon)$. Thus, the effective bath takes the simple form $\mathcal{G}_0^{-1} = i\omega_n + \mu$, the effective action is the action of a single site of the atomic Hubbard model. The problem is no longer k -dependent, and we have $G_{0\text{imp}} = \mathcal{G}_0^{-1} = G_{0\text{loc}}$ and the impurity model yields the exact local Green's function. [27]

⁴Again the steps are shown in appendix B; we obtain the following relations by replacing the sums over the cavity Green's functions in the effective bath eq. (2.32) and the hybridization function eq. (2.33) by eq. (B.17).

2.2. Real space dynamical mean-field theory (r-DMFT)

So far we only considered translation invariant lattice systems. In this thesis however, we are interested in inhomogeneous systems, namely layered heterostructures. Thus, in the following we reformulate the DMFT scheme introduced in section 2.1. In contrast to the homogeneous case, the Green's function is not diagonal in k -space. Also, we cannot map the problem to a single impurity and use the self-energy for all sites, as not all sites are equivalent. The outline is the following: We will first derive an approximation, in which the self-energy is local with respect to the layers. In this approximation, we can apply the DMFT for the single layers. Then we introduce a basis, which is suitable to treat the Green's functions. In this basis we will formulate an algorithm, how to treat our heterostructures. First we introduce a suitable notation for the layered structure. Let the layers be stacked along the z -direction. The position of a site α in a layer l is denoted by the vector $\mathbf{r}_i \equiv r_l \mathbf{e}_z + \mathbf{r}_\alpha$. In the following the indices l (and l') always denote layers, and α (and β) always denote sites within a layer. A layer has at most two adjacent neighbors, thus we have a low coordination number with respect to the layers. We cannot employ the limit of infinite coordination number. Consequently, contributions of the self-energy, that are non-local, do not vanish in general. Thus, the self-energy is a matrix $\Sigma_{ll'}$.

In the following we are mainly interested in the intralayer hopping elements.⁵ We introduce the multi-indices $i = (l\alpha)$ and $j = (l'\beta)$; the hopping matrix elements of eqs. (2.1) and (2.3) read

$$t_{ij} \equiv t_{l\alpha;l'\beta}. \quad (2.38)$$

We split the hopping elements $t_{l\alpha;l'\beta}$ into interlayer and intralayer elements

$$\begin{aligned} t_{l\alpha;l'\beta} &= t_{l\alpha;l'\beta} \delta_{ll'} + t_{l\alpha;l'\beta} (1 - \delta_{ll'}) \\ &=: t_{\alpha\beta}^l + T_{l\alpha;l'\beta}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.39)$$

We will introduce auxiliary fields and expand the contributions of the isolated layers in cumulants. We truncate this expansion after the first order, keeping only the quadratic part in the auxiliary fields. This approximation results in a self-energy which is diagonal in the layers $\Sigma_{l\alpha;l'\beta} = \Sigma_{\alpha\beta}^l \delta_{ll'}$. We start from the action S of the heterostructure, which we split into two parts

$$S = \sum_l S_l + \Delta S. \quad (2.40)$$

S_l is the action of the isolated layer l , and ΔS contains the hopping in between the layers

$$S_l = \int_0^\beta d\tau \left(\sum_{\alpha\beta} \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} [(\partial_\tau - \mu_l + \epsilon_l) \delta_{\alpha\beta} + t_{\alpha\beta}^l] c_{l\beta\sigma} + \sum_\alpha U_l n_{l\alpha\uparrow} n_{l\alpha\downarrow} \right) \quad (2.41)$$

$$\Delta S = \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{ll'} \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} T_{l\alpha;l'\beta} c_{l'\beta\sigma}. \quad (2.42)$$

⁵Analogous to the homogeneous DMFT in section 2.1, the explicit structure and hopping within layers are not relevant. Only the non-interacting density of states of the layers enters in the end.

We sum the indices l and l' over all layers and α and β over all sites within a layer. The corresponding partition function writes

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{c}, c] e^{-S[\bar{c}, c]} = \left[\prod_{l'} \mathcal{Z}_{l'} \right] \left\langle e^{-\Delta S} \right\rangle_{\sum_l S_l}. \quad (2.43)$$

We perform the *Grassmannian Hubbard-Stratonovich* transformation following [28]. We rewrite $e^{-\Delta S}$ as Gaussian integral (compare eq. (A.31)) over auxiliary Grassmann fields $\psi_{l\alpha\sigma}(\tau)$ and $\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma}(\tau)$:

$$\begin{aligned} e^{-\Delta S} &= e^{-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{ll'} \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} T_{l\alpha;l'\beta} c_{l'\beta\sigma}} \\ &= \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_0} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] e^{\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} \sum_{ll'} \bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} (T^{-1})_{l\alpha;l'\beta} \psi_{l'\beta\sigma} - \sum_{\alpha\sigma} \sum_l (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.44)$$

We introduce the non-interacting auxiliary action

$$\mathcal{S}_0[\bar{\psi}, \psi] = - \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} \sum_{ll'} \bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} (T^{-1})_{l\alpha;l'\beta} \psi_{l'\beta\sigma}, \quad (2.45)$$

\mathcal{Z}_0 is the corresponding partition function

$$\mathcal{Z}_0 = \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] e^{-\mathcal{S}_0}. \quad (2.46)$$

We use eq. (2.44) to rewrite the partition function \mathcal{Z} eq. (2.43) as a field integral over the auxiliary fields:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{Z} &= \left[\prod_{l'} \mathcal{Z}_{l'} \right] \left\langle e^{-\Delta S} \right\rangle_{\sum_l S_l} \\ &= \left[\prod_{l'} \mathcal{Z}_{l'} \right] \left\langle \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}_0} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] e^{-\mathcal{S}_0[\bar{\psi}, \psi] - \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} \sum_l (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})} \right\rangle_{\sum_l S_l} \\ &= \frac{[\prod_{l'} \mathcal{Z}_{l'}]}{\mathcal{Z}_0} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] e^{-\mathcal{S}_0[\bar{\psi}, \psi]} \left\langle e^{-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} \sum_l (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})} \right\rangle_{\sum_l S_l}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.47)$$

In the second line we plugged eq. (2.44) in; in the third line we pulled out all terms that are only functionals of the auxiliary fields ψ and $\bar{\psi}$ and not of c and \bar{c} . We can further

split the average $\langle \cdot \rangle_{\sum_l S_l}$ into the contributions of the isolated layers, as the average contains no interlayer terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int \prod_l \mathcal{D}[\bar{c}_l, c_l] e^{-\sum_l S_l} \exp\left(-\sum_l \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})\right) \\
 &= \prod_l \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{c}_l, c_l] e^{-S_l} \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})\right) \\
 &= \prod_l \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})\right) \right\rangle_{S_l}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.48}$$

Thus, we write

$$\mathcal{Z} = \frac{[\prod_{l'} \mathcal{Z}_{l'}]}{\mathcal{Z}_0} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] e^{-\mathcal{S}_0[\bar{\psi}, \psi]} \prod_l \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})\right) \right\rangle_{S_l}. \tag{2.49}$$

We re-exponentiate the average $\langle \cdot \rangle_{S_l}$. In the same fashion as eq. (2.29), we can expand the logarithm of averages $\langle \cdot \rangle_{S_l}$ in terms of connected Green's functions

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \ln \left\langle \exp\left(-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\sigma} (\bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} c_{l\alpha\sigma} + \bar{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} \psi_{l\alpha\sigma})\right) \right\rangle_{S_l} \\
 &= -\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum'_{\alpha_1 \dots \beta_n} \int d\tau_1 \dots \int d\tau'_n \bar{\psi}_{l\beta_1} \dots \bar{\psi}_{l\beta_n} \psi_{l\alpha_1} \dots \psi_{l\alpha_n} G_{c \alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n; \beta_1 \dots \beta_n}^l,
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.50}$$

with $G_{c \alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n; \beta_1 \dots \beta_n}^l = -\langle c_{l\alpha_1} \dots c_{l\alpha_n} \bar{c}_{l\beta_1} \dots \bar{c}_{l\beta_n} \rangle_{S_l c}$, and the prime at the sum denotes an ordered sum.⁶ We suppress the σ -indices.

The next step is to establish a relation between fermionic Green's functions G of the full lattice and auxiliary field Green's functions \mathcal{G} . To shorten the notation we introduce new indices a and b , which denote sets $(l, \alpha, \sigma, \tau)$. Evidently a fermionic n -particle Green's function can be generated by differentiating the average $\langle \dots \rangle_{(\sum_l S_l)}$ in eq. (2.49) with respect to the auxiliary fields

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{a_1 \dots a_n b_1 \dots b_n}^{(n)} &= -\langle c_{a_1} \dots c_{a_n} \bar{c}_{b_1} \dots \bar{c}_{b_n} \rangle_S \\
 &= -\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] e^{-\mathcal{S}_0} \frac{\delta^{2n}}{\delta \psi_{b_1} \dots \delta \psi_{b_n} \delta \bar{\psi}_{a_1} \dots \delta \bar{\psi}_{a_n}} \left\langle e^{-\sum_a (\bar{\psi}_a c_a + \bar{c}_a \psi_a)} \right\rangle_{\sum_l S_l}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.51}$$

⁶Formally this expansion looks identical to eq. (2.29). In eq. (2.29) however, the source terms η are proportional to the hopping which will be scaled in the limit of infinite coordination number. In eq. (2.50) on the other hand, higher orders n do not vanish in general in this limit.

Using integration by parts as defined in [29] we can relate G to the auxiliary fields Green's functions

$$G_{a_1 \dots a_n b_1 \dots b_n}^{(n)} = -\frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\psi}, \psi] \left(e^{-\mathcal{S}_0} \frac{\overleftarrow{\delta}^{2n}}{\delta \psi_{b_1} \dots \delta \psi_{b_n} \delta \bar{\psi}_{a_1} \dots \delta \bar{\psi}_{a_n}} \right) \langle e^{-\sum_a (\bar{\psi}_a c_a + \bar{c}_a \psi_a)} \rangle_{\sum_l S_l}. \quad (2.52)$$

The arrow in this equation indicates that the right derivative [29] is used, this means the derivative acts from the right side on the Grassmann fields. We explicitly calculate the expression for the one-particle Green's function. The differentiation yields:

$$\left(e^{-\mathcal{S}_0} \frac{\overleftarrow{\delta}^2}{\delta \psi_a \delta \bar{\psi}_b} \right) = e^{-\mathcal{S}_0} \left((T^{-1})_{ab} + \sum_{a'b'} (T^{-1})_{ab'} \psi_{b'} \bar{\psi}_{a'} (T^{-1})_{a'b} \right) \quad (2.53)$$

and thus the one-particle Green's function is

$$G_{ab} \equiv G_{ab}^{(1)} = -(T^{-1})_{ba} + \sum_{a'b'} (T^{-1})_{ba'} \mathcal{G}_{a'b'} (T^{-1})_{b'a}. \quad (2.54)$$

We still need to calculate the auxiliary field Green's function \mathcal{G} . Now we approximate the expansion eq. (2.50) by truncating it. We only keep the first order $n = 1$, thus the action is quadratic in the auxiliary field

$$\mathcal{S} = \int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} \sum_{l'} \bar{\psi}_{l\alpha\sigma} \left(-(T^{-1})_{l\alpha;l'\beta} + \delta_{ll'} G_{\alpha\beta\sigma}^l \right) \psi_{l'\beta\sigma}. \quad (2.55)$$

We can directly obtain the auxiliary fields Green's function \mathcal{G} from eq. (2.55) via Gaussian integration

$$\mathcal{G}_{ab} = \left(T^{-1} - \text{diag}(G^l) \right)_{ab}^{-1}. \quad (2.56)$$

We plug this back into eq. (2.54) and obtain the matrix equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G} &= -\mathbf{T}^{-1} + \mathbf{T}^{-1} \left(\mathbf{T}^{-1} - \text{diag}(G^l) \right)^{-1} \mathbf{T}^{-1} \\ &= \left(\text{diag}(G^l)^{-1} - \mathbf{T} \right)^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.57)$$

The second equality is the Woodbury matrix identity [30]. Thus, we can calculate the Green's function G of the full heterostructure from the Green's functions of the isolated layers G^l . Written in terms of the self-energy we get

$$\mathbf{G}^{-1} = \text{diag} \left(i\omega_n + \mu_l - \epsilon_l - \Sigma'_l(i\omega_n) \right) - \mathbf{T}, \quad (2.58)$$

where the self-energies Σ'_l are determined by the Dyson equations of the isolated layers

$$\Sigma'_l = G_0^{l-1} - G^{l-1}. \quad (2.59)$$

We can determine these self-energies Σ'_l by using DMFT for every distinct isolated layer. This approximation is evidently correct in the limit of isolated layers $T = 0$, and the limit of non-interacting layers $U_l = 0$. This approximation is supplemented by self-consistency.

Self-consistent r-DMFT equations. We are going to replace the self-energy of the isolated layers Σ'_l by a self-consistently determined self-energy. We can also write eq. (2.58) in the form

$$\mathbf{G}^{-1} = \text{diag} \left((\mathbf{G}^{-1})_{ll} \right) - \mathbf{T}, \quad (2.60)$$

we simply wrote the inverse Green's function as sum of the diagonal and the off-diagonal elements. The Green's function reads then

$$\mathbf{G} = \left(\text{diag} \left((\mathbf{G}^{-1})_{ll} \right) - \mathbf{T} \right)^{-1}. \quad (2.61)$$

This looks like a self-consistent equation, because it involves the same Green's function \mathbf{G} on the left and right of the equation. The Dyson equation for the self-energy reads then

$$\Sigma_l = G_{0l}^{-1} - G_l^{-1}. \quad (2.62)$$

We will determine the self-energy Σ_l by an r-DMFT scheme, which will be given later in algorithm 2, instead of using Σ'_l from eq. (2.59).

Before further explaining how to calculate the self-energy, we perform a Fourier transform within the layers following the description of [15]. The direction perpendicular to the layers is treated in real space. In the layers the translational invariance is preserved, but it is lost in the perpendicular direction. Due to translational invariance in x - and y - direction, the two-dimensional Fourier transform diagonalizes the Green's function within the layers. The two-dimensional Fourier transform for the hopping $t_{ij} = t_{l\alpha;l'\beta}$ yields the general dispersion matrix

$$\epsilon_{ll'}(k) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N^l N^{l'}}} \sum_{\alpha\beta} t_{l\alpha;l'\beta} e^{ik(r_\alpha - r_\beta)}. \quad (2.63)$$

N^l is the number of sites in layer l . We will only consider interlayer hopping to the corresponding site in the layers $T_{l\alpha;l'\beta} = \delta_{\alpha\beta} t_{ll'}$ for $l \neq l'$.⁷ In this case the off-diagonal terms of eq. (2.63) are k -independent:

$$\epsilon_{ll'}(k) = T_{l0;l'0} \equiv t_{ll'} \quad \text{for } l \neq l'. \quad (2.64)$$

Again we consider the limit of infinite coordination number $Z \rightarrow \infty$, but only the in-plane neighbors are considered. In this limit the self-energy becomes local within the layers $\Sigma_{l\alpha;l'\beta} \rightarrow \Sigma_{l\alpha;l\alpha} \delta_{\alpha\beta} \delta_{ll'}$, the locality $\delta_{ll'}$ is the consequence of our approximation. Thus, after the Fourier transform, the self-energy is independent of the two-dimensional k : $\Sigma_{ll'}(k, i\omega_n) \rightarrow \Sigma_{ll'}(i\omega_n)$. We introduce the shorthand notation

$$\xi_l(i\omega_n) := i\omega_n + \mu_l - \epsilon_{ll} - \Sigma_l(i\omega_n). \quad (2.65)$$

⁷To write it in this simple form, we assume that all layers are structural identical and have the same number of sites $N^l = N_{\parallel}$.

The two-dimensional Fourier transformed Green's function eq. (2.61) writes

$$\mathbf{G}^{-1}(k, i\omega_n) = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_1(i\omega_n) - \epsilon_{11}(k) & t_{12} & t_{13} & \dots \\ t_{21} & \xi_2(i\omega_n) - \epsilon_{22}(k) & t_{23} & \\ t_{31} & t_{32} & \xi_3(i\omega_n) - \epsilon_{33}(k) & \\ \vdots & & & \ddots \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.66)$$

This problem can now in principle be treated analogous to the homogeneous case.

To obtain the local Green's function we need to invert the Green's function eq. (2.66) for every k and $i\omega_n$ point. It is more convenient to first diagonalize the k -independent part of the matrix, and work with the eigendecomposition [31]. For DMFT the k -dependency only enters by the non-interacting density of states, thus we can work with $\mathbf{G}(\epsilon, i\omega_n)$ instead of $\mathbf{G}(k, i\omega_n) \equiv \mathbf{G}(\epsilon_k, i\omega_n)$. We assume all (isolated) layers to have the same structure and thus have the same two-dimensional dispersion $\epsilon_{ll} = \epsilon$. We split off the ϵ and diagonalize the ϵ -independent rest of the matrix

$$\mathbf{G}^{-1}(\epsilon, i\omega_n) = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_1(i\omega_n) & t_{12} & t_{13} & \dots \\ t_{21} & \xi_2(i\omega_n) & t_{23} & \\ t_{31} & t_{32} & \xi_3(i\omega_n) & \\ \vdots & & & \ddots \end{pmatrix} - \epsilon \mathbf{1} \quad (2.67)$$

$$= \mathbf{V}(i\omega_n) \text{diag}(\tilde{\xi}_l(i\omega_n)) \mathbf{V}^{-1}(i\omega_n) - \epsilon \mathbf{1} \quad (2.68)$$

$$= \mathbf{V}(i\omega_n) [\text{diag}(\tilde{\xi}_l(i\omega_n)) - \epsilon \mathbf{1}] \mathbf{V}^{-1}(i\omega_n). \quad (2.69)$$

In the second line we replaced the matrix by its eigendecomposition; $\tilde{\xi}_l(i\omega_n)$ are the eigenvalues of the ϵ -independent part of the inverse Green's function. The inverse is

$$\mathbf{G}(\epsilon, i\omega_n) = \mathbf{V}(i\omega_n) \text{diag}\left(\frac{1}{\tilde{\xi}_l(i\omega_n) - \epsilon}\right) \mathbf{V}^{-1}(i\omega_n). \quad (2.70)$$

The local Green's function takes then the simple form

$$\mathbf{G}(i\omega_n) = \mathbf{V}(i\omega_n) \text{diag}\left(\int d\epsilon \frac{\rho(\epsilon)}{\tilde{\xi}_l(i\omega_n) - \epsilon}\right) \mathbf{V}^{-1}(i\omega_n), \quad (2.71)$$

where we integrate over the layer DOS $\rho(\epsilon) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_k \delta(\epsilon - \epsilon_k)$.

Now we can reformulate the DMFT algorithm 1 for the layered heterostructures. For every distinct layer, a separate impurity problem needs to be solved. We calculate the local Green's function $G_{ll}(i\omega)$ from eq. (2.71). We then define the impurity by the effective bath using equation eq. (2.35):

$$\mathcal{G}_{0l}^{-1}(i\omega_n) = \Sigma_l(i\omega_n) + G_{ll}^{-1}(i\omega_n). \quad (2.72)$$

This step is ad hoc at this point. The derivation of eq. (2.35) in appendix B assumes that the local self-energy $\Sigma_l(i\omega_n)$ is identical to the local self-energy for the cavity system

$\Sigma_l^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n)$, where one site was removed. As we only have two interlayer neighbors, one in each adjacent layer, this assumption cannot be justified in the same way as for the homogeneous system. We still use eq. (2.72) without any further justification. For every distinct layer, an impurity problem $G_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_{0l}]$ must be solved. Then the self energies obtained from these impurity problems are put back into eq. (2.71), to obtain the new lattice Green's function of our heterostructure. While every impurity problem yields an independent self-energy Σ_l , they are coupled by the matrix inversion in eq. (2.71). The new algorithm is given in algorithm 2. [15]

$\Sigma_l(i\omega_n) := \Sigma_{l\text{initial}}(i\omega_n)$
repeat
 $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{G}(i\omega_n) := \mathbf{V}(i\omega_n) \text{diag} \left(\int d\epsilon \frac{\rho(\epsilon)}{\xi_l(i\omega_n) - \epsilon} \right) \mathbf{V}^{-1}(i\omega_n) \\ \mathcal{G}_{0l}^{-1}(i\omega_n) := G_{ll}^{-1}(i\omega_n) + \Sigma_l(i\omega_n) \\ \text{solve impurity problems } G_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_{0l}] \\ \Sigma_l(i\omega_n) := \mathcal{G}_{0l}^{-1}(i\omega_n) - G_{\text{imp}}^{-1}(i\omega_n) \end{array} \right.$
until *self-consistency*

Algorithm 2: Self-consistent r-DMFT equations.

2.3. Poisson equation for a layered heterostructure

We now extend the Hubbard model eq. (2.1) by including non-local Coulomb interactions, which we treat on a mean-field level. We will calculate the classical electrical potential energy V and include it in the chemical potential μ , thus upgrading it to an electrochemical potential

$$\mu_l^{\text{el}} = \mu_l - V_l. \quad (2.73)$$

The electrical potential energy of a layer is then $\langle \hat{n}_l \rangle V_l$. This is a mean-field approximate for a direct Coulomb interaction

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{l'} V_{ll'} \hat{n}_{l'} \hat{n}_l \approx \sum_{l'} V_{ll'} \langle \hat{n}_{l'} \rangle \hat{n}_l =: \sum_{l'} V_l \hat{n}_l, \quad (2.74)$$

with the mean-field $V_l = \sum_{l'} V_{ll'} \langle \hat{n}_{l'} \rangle$.

We assume the layers to be uniformly charged planes with charge density ρ_l , equidistant spacing a , and the electrical permittivity ε_l to be constant for every layer as proposed in [7]. So the electrical permittivity is a piecewise constant function $\varepsilon(z) = \varepsilon_l$ in the interval $[\frac{r_{l-1}+r_l}{2}, \frac{r_l+r_{l+1}}{2}]$, and can change at the midpoint of two layers. Due to the in-plane translational symmetry, the problem of calculating the classical potential Φ is a quasi one-dimensional problem. The electrical field generated by the plane l is piecewise constant [32]

$$|E^l(z)| = \frac{\rho_l}{2\varepsilon(z)}. \quad (2.75)$$

We can calculate the potential *generated* by the layer l by integrating the electrical field E_l

$$\Phi^l(z) = - \int_{r_l}^z dz' E^\alpha(z') + \Phi^l(r_l), \quad (2.76)$$

where r_l denotes the position of the layer. We choose $\Phi^l(r_l) \equiv 0$, thus it is compatible with the on-site interactions that are already included in U_l . Evaluating the integral and summing over all lattice sites yields the total electrical potential energy at site l

$$V_l = -e\Phi(z_\beta) = - \sum_m n_m \sum_{n=\min(m,l)+1}^{\max(m,l)} \frac{1}{2} (e_{\text{schot}}^n + e_{\text{schot}}^{n-1}). \quad (2.77)$$

The l , n and m denote layer indices, and we introduced the quantity $e_{\text{schot}}^l := \frac{e^2 a}{2\epsilon_l}$ and the electron density $n_l = \langle \hat{n}_l \rangle$ with $-en_l = \rho_l$.

We include the Coulomb potential of the ions in the same fashion using the same model. Thus, we get the same expression, just with opposite sign. We call their charge density ρ^{bulk} , it is not subject to charge reconstructions. To fulfill charge neutrality, the relation $\sum_l \rho_l = \sum_l \rho_l^{\text{bulk}}$ must hold. For simplicity, we will choose a constant density $\rho = \rho^{\text{bulk}} := \sum_\alpha \rho_\alpha$. So finally we obtain the same result as [7] for the potential:

$$V_l = - \sum_m (n_m - n^{\text{bulk}}) \sum_{n=\min(m,l)+1}^{\max(m,l)} \frac{1}{2} (e_{\text{schot}}^n + e_{\text{schot}}^{n-1}), \quad (2.78)$$

where we introduced $en^{\text{bulk}} = \rho^{\text{bulk}}$.

We will only study symmetric systems with a constant $e_{\text{schot}}^l \equiv e_{\text{schot}}$, thus we further investigate this setup. For simplicity, we set $e_{\text{schot}} = 1$ and define $\Delta n_l := n_l - n^{\text{bulk}}$. We label our layers with the indices $l \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. For the outermost layer we get

$$V_1 = V_N = - \sum_l \Delta n_l |l - 1| = - \sum_l l \Delta n_l + \sum_l \Delta n_l. \quad (2.79)$$

Using the symmetry we can now eliminate l in the sum and obtain:

$$V_1 = - \frac{N+1}{2} \sum_l \Delta n_l + \sum_l \Delta n_l = \frac{-N+1}{2} \Delta n_{\text{total}}. \quad (2.80)$$

Due to charge neutrality the potential vanishes for the layers at the outer margin for a symmetric setup with constant e_{schot}^l .

2.4. A combination of the r-DMFT with the Poisson equation

We combine the Coulomb potential obtained in section 2.3 with the r-DMFT algorithm 2 from section 2.2. The combined scheme is depicted in fig. 2.2. We start from the action eq. (2.40) or the corresponding Hamiltonian, where we replaced the chemical potential by

Figure 2.2: Combined scheme of *r*-DMFT and Coulomb potential.

the electrochemical potential $\mu_l \rightarrow \mu_l^{\text{el}} = \mu_l - V_l$, and an initial self-energy $\Sigma_l^{\text{initial}}$. With this input we run the *r*-DMFT [33] loop described in algorithm 2 in section 2.2. We use a continuous-time hybridization-expansion quantum Monte Carlo (CT-Hyb) solver [34] for the impurity problem. This is the inner loop in the blue box of fig. 2.2.

We use the occupations n_l obtained from the impurity solutions $G_{\text{imp}}[\mathcal{G}_{0l}]$ to calculate the Coulomb potential V_l eq. (2.78). We update the parameter in our Hamiltonian, however the occupations is sensitive to V_l , so we only mix in little of our new potential

$$V_l^{\text{new}} \simeq mV_l^{\text{new}} + (1 - m)V_l^{\text{old}}. \quad (2.81)$$

The mixing parameter is usually around $m \simeq 0.01$. This outer loop will be repeated until the occupation of the layers n_l does not change anymore. This charge self-consistency loop takes, depending on the initial guess for the potential V_l , many iterations due to the small mixing m .

The computational intensive part of this algorithm is the inner *r*-DMFT loop, therefore we usually only run one iteration of this inner loop, and immediately update the potential. Sometimes more iterations are necessary to calculate the new V_l , as a sufficient converged occupation n_l is needed. We usually proceed as following: in the first iteration we run the inner *r*-DMFT loop until self-consistency. Then we run the outer loop, terminating the *r*-DMFT loop after only a single iteration, until charge self-consistency is achieved. And finally we run further iterations of the inner *r*-DMFT self-consistency loop, to obtain more accurate Green's functions.

3. Results

3.1. The system setup

We model an interface between a half-metal and non-interacting leads. The basic setup that we are going to study consists of one interacting half-metallic layer sandwiched between 19 non-interacting non-magnetic layers on each side. Figure 3.1 shows the

Figure 3.1: Layer geometry of the heterostructure. The central blue layer is half-metallic. The surrounding orange layers are non-magnetic.

schematic layout. We start from a single-band Hubbard model with the action eq. (2.40). We need to include a magnetic field h_l in form of a Zeeman term. Our single-band Hamiltonian is non-magnetic, thus the field is necessary to model the half-metallic layer. To allow for charge reconstructions, we furthermore include interlayer Coulomb interaction on a mean-field level as Coulomb potential. We simply refer to it as the Coulomb potential V_l . We include the Coulomb potential from section 2.3 by upgrading the chemical potential to an electrochemical potential $\mu_l \rightarrow \mu_l^{el}$. The Hamiltonian for the system is given by

$$\hat{H} = \sum_l \hat{H}_l + \sum_{\langle l, l' \rangle} \Delta \hat{H}_{ll'}; \quad (3.1)$$

it is separated into contributions of the isolated layers \hat{H}_l and the interlayer part $\Delta \hat{H}_{ll'}$ between adjacent layers. The interlayer Hamiltonian is given by

$$\Delta \hat{H}_{ll'} = \sum_{\alpha\sigma} t_{ll'} \hat{c}_{l\alpha\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{l'\alpha\sigma} = -t \sum_{\alpha\sigma} \hat{c}_{l\alpha\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{l'\alpha\sigma}; \quad (3.2)$$

we only consider uniform hopping $t_{ll'} = t$. The Hamiltonian \hat{H}_l for the isolated layer l is given by

$$\hat{H}_l = \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} t_{\alpha\beta}^l \hat{c}_{l\alpha\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{l\beta\sigma} + \sum_{\alpha\sigma} (-\mu_l^{el} + \sigma h_l) \hat{c}_{l\alpha\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{l\alpha\sigma} + U_l \sum_{\alpha} \hat{n}_{l\alpha\uparrow} \hat{n}_{l\alpha\downarrow}. \quad (3.3)$$

The spin σ takes the values $\sigma = \pm\frac{1}{2}$ and the electrochemical potential⁸ is $\mu_l^{el} = \mu_l - V_l$ as explained in section 2.3. We study symmetric setups. The central layer $l = 0$ is half-metallic and can be interacting. The surrounding leads are modeled by 19 layers on each side. All surrounding layers $l \neq 0$ will be non-interacting $U_{l \neq 0} = 0$ and non-magnetic $h_{l \neq 0} = 0$. We choose the chemical potential in such a way that these layers are half-filled $\mu_{l \neq 0} = \frac{U_l}{2} = 0$.⁹ Consequently, the part $\hat{H}_{l \neq 0}$ takes the simple form

$$\hat{H}_{l \neq 0} = \sum_{\alpha\beta\sigma} (t_{\alpha\beta}^l + V_l \delta_{\alpha\beta}) \hat{c}_{l\alpha\sigma}^\dagger \hat{c}_{l\beta\sigma}. \quad (3.4)$$

For the layer DOS, see eq. (2.71), we choose a semicircular DOS with half-bandwidth D for all layers. This corresponds to a Bethe lattice, with the nearest neighbor (NN) hopping $t_{\alpha\beta}^l = t_{NN} = D/2$ in plane and infinite coordination number. The half-bandwidth defines the energy scale, we set $D \equiv 1$. We performed all calculations for the temperature $T/D = 0.01$. The hopping between the layers is fixed to $t/D = 0.2$. The parameter e_l^{shot} for the Coulomb potential eq. (2.78) is fixed at constant $e_l^{\text{shot}}/D = 0.4$ for all layers.

For the half-metallic layer $l = 0$ we will consider the parameters $\mu_0 = 0.45D + \frac{U_0}{2}$ and $h_0/D = -0.9$, making the spin-up channel half filled $n_\uparrow = 0.5$ like the surrounding layers, and the spin-down channel almost completely filled $n_\downarrow \approx 1$. The parameters are chosen such that for the interacting case $U_0/D = 0.8$ the spectral function for majority spin $\sigma = \downarrow$ will vanish roughly around the Fermi level. In the following we will investigate one-particle quantities for this setup.

3.2. Non-interacting case

Non-interacting system without Coulomb potential. We first study the basic system with neither interaction nor Coulomb potential as a reference. Figure 3.2 shows the layer and spin resolved spectral functions $A_{l\sigma}(\omega) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \Im G_{l\sigma}(\omega + i0^+)$. The spectral functions are broadened compared to the semicircular DOS of isolated layers; they display shoulders outside of the bandwidth of the isolated layers. In the non-interacting case, the $\sigma = \uparrow$ channel and the $\sigma = \downarrow$ decouple. Thus, for all layers, the spectral functions $A_{l\uparrow}$ of the minority spin are identical except for boundary effects.

In the central half-metallic layer, the spectral function $A_{0\downarrow}(\omega)$ for the majority spin is shifted down in energy compared to the system with isolated layers. Thus, its amplitude decreases at the Fermi-level $\omega = 0$. The spectral function $A_{0\downarrow}$ has a rather long ranged tail for positive frequencies ω . This tail is a result of the hybridization with the surrounding layers; its amplitude is controlled by the parameter t . Larger interlayer hopping leads to an increase of the amplitude of the tail. In the layer $l = 1$ next to the half-metallic layer, the spectral function $A_{1\downarrow}$ displays a small decrease in amplitude around $\omega = 0$ for positive frequencies. The charge transfer necessary to build the tail in $A_{0\downarrow}$ induces this

⁸The Coulomb potential V_l is conceptionally an interlayer contribution, it is however more convenient to include it in \hat{H}_l .

⁹For isolated layers this chemical potential results in half filling. The filling of layers of the heterostructure may change depending on the surrounding layers.

Figure 3.2: Layer and spin resolved spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ for the non-interacting case without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$. For every layer the up-spin (\uparrow) is shown to the left, and the down-spin (\downarrow) is mirrored to the right. We show only one half of the symmetric setup and truncate after the sixth layer. The dashed lines are the spectral function for isolated layers, this means $t = 0$.

decrease. Thus, the decrease starts at the same frequency, at which the spectral function $A_{0\downarrow}$ displays a kink and transitions into the tail. Analogous to the tail of $A_{0\downarrow}$, the spectral function $A_{1\downarrow}$ in the adjacent layer has a tail for low frequencies. Including these tails, both the spectral functions $A_{0\downarrow}$ and $A_{1\downarrow}$ have the same bandwidths. While both adjacent layers of the central layer $l = 0$ have spectral weight for positive frequencies, only one layer ($l = 0$) adjacent to the layer $l = 1$ has spectral weight for lower frequencies. Thus, the tail of $A_{1\downarrow}$ is smaller in amplitude and hardly visible. In the layer $l = 2$, the low frequency tail is still present. It is however an order of magnitude smaller than in layer $l = 1$. Thus, from layer $l = 2$ on, we cannot see anymore a clear difference from the homogeneous system, where all layers are non-magnetic with $h_l, \mu_l, U_l = 0$.

Inclusion of the interlayer Coulomb potential. The interlayer Coulomb interaction is self-consistently included on a mean-field level as Coulomb potential, like we explained in section 2.3. The upper half (a) of fig. 3.3 compares the occupation to the

Figure 3.3: Effect of Coulomb potential in the non-interacting case $U_0 \equiv 0$. The upper half (a) shows the spin resolved filling of the layers $n_{l\sigma}$. Here the dotted lines n_{σ}^0 denote the occupation without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$. The lower half (b) shows the self-consistently calculated Coulomb potential V_l . The parameters of the calculation are given in the legend.

case without the potential V_l ; the lower half (b) shows the potential V_l itself. The results are what we expect from classical electrostatics. The central layer carries more charge than the surrounding layers. Without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$, the net occupation is $\Delta n_{l=0}^0 = n_{l=0}^0 - n^{\text{bulk}} \simeq 0.45$ as shown in fig. 3.4a. This net charge creates a repulsive potential. The non-interacting layers screen the potential; after 5 layers it already

dropped to $V_5/D = 1.67 \cdot 10^{-3}$, so it decreased to less than one percent of the value at the central layer $V_5/V_0 = 9.06 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

Figure 3.4: Effect of Coulomb potential V_l on the spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ in the non-interacting case $U_0 = 0$. The left side (a) shows the layer and spin resolved spectral function without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$; it is the same as the solid lines in fig. 3.2. The right side (b) shows the corresponding spectral function including the Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$. The spectral functions $A_{l\downarrow}$ of the down-spin (\downarrow) are mirrored down.

Figure 3.4 shows the spectral functions $A_{l\sigma}$ for the calculations without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$ on the left (a), and including Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$ on the right (b). The main effect of the Coulomb potential V_l on the spectral functions is a rigid shift. If we look at the inverse Green's function, the potential V_l only shifts the ω in the diagonal elements

$$G_{0l}^{-1}(\omega) = \omega + (\mu_l - V_l) - \epsilon = G_{0l}^{-1}|_{V_l=0}(\omega - V_l). \quad (3.5)$$

Thus, the shift of the spectral functions is expected to be the dominant change. In the non-interacting case, this is the only effect for vanishing interlayer hopping $t = 0$. Changes in shape of $A_{l\sigma} = -\frac{1}{\pi} \Im G_{l\sigma}$ are corrections due to the presence of t , appearing

Figure 3.5: Spin and layer resolved spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ for the central and first layer with and without including Coulomb potential V_l . The spectral function is plotted over $\omega - V_l$ to compensate the effect of the rigid shift due to the potential, thus changes in shape become visible. The spectral function labeled $V_l \equiv 0$ ($V_l \neq 0$) is the one shown in fig. 3.4a (fig. 3.4b). The spectral function labeled $t = 0$ is for isolated layers and plotted as a reference.

during the matrix inversion. Figure 3.5 collapses the spectral functions $A_{l\sigma}$ without and including Coulomb potential V_l by plotting them over $\omega - V_l$. For the most part, the two spectral functions agree. The effects of the potential V_l visible in fig. 3.5 are:

- (i) the appearance of a kink in $A_{0\uparrow}$ around $\omega \approx -0.6$,
- (ii) the change of the tail for positive frequencies ω in $A_{0\downarrow}$,
- (iii) the shift of the decrease in amplitude of $A_{1\downarrow}$ to higher frequencies.

The cause of the shift (iii) is, that this decrease is at the same point in frequency, where the spectral function $A_{0\downarrow}$ transitions into the tail. Thus, the much larger $V_{l=0}$ determines its position and not $V_{l=1}$. Figure 3.4 shows that the decrease in $A_{1\downarrow}$ is at the same position as the start of the positive frequency tail in $A_{0\downarrow}$. Thus, (iii) is no effect of the potential V_l , but of the interlayer hopping t . So in order to obtain effects beyond the shift, we would have to increase the strength of the interlayer hopping t or consider stronger a Coulomb potential V_l .

Let us consider the half-metallic layer $l = 0$ again. A measure of half-metallicity is the polarization of the spectral function at the Fermi level:

$$P_{A_0} = \frac{A_{0\uparrow}(0) - A_{0\downarrow}(0)}{A_{0\uparrow}(0) + A_{0\downarrow}(0)}. \quad (3.6)$$

According to this criterion, the presence of the Coulomb potential V_l is unfavorable for the half-metallicity. The potential shifts the weight of the spectral function $A_{0\downarrow}$ towards the Fermi level. Thus, the polarization of the spectral function P_{A_0} for the central layer $l = 0$ decreases. In the case without Coulomb potential $V_l = 0$, it takes the values $P_{A_0} = 0.61$; including the Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$, it decreases to $P_{A_0} = 0.20$.

3.3. Interacting case

Next we consider the case, that the central half-metallic layer is interacting $U_0 \neq 0$. In the interacting case, the spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega) = -\frac{1}{\pi}\Im G_{l\sigma}(\omega + i0^+)$ has to be carefully computed. We use CT-Hyb [34] as impurity solver, thus we calculated imaginary-time Green's functions $G_{l\sigma}(\tau)$. To get the Green's functions on the real frequency axis, we need to perform an analytical continuation. This is sensitive to numerical errors, consequently there are artifacts in our plot. We perform the Padé analytical continuation [35, 36] with different numbers of Matsubara points. Features that do not change by varying the number of Matsubara points are physical. Peaks that appear just for different numbers of points are taken to be artifacts. The shaded area in our plots is the standard deviation of the results, where we performed Padé with different number of Matsubara points. Though this is not an error estimate, the results with low standard deviation should be reliable. A more detailed analysis of the Padé analytical continuation is given in appendix D.

Figure 3.6: Layer and spin resolved spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ for the interacting case $U_0 = 0.8$ without Coulomb potential $V_l = 0$. The dashed lines are the spectral function for the non-interacting case $U_0 = 0$ without Coulomb potential $V_l = 0$. It is the same spectral function shown in fig. 3.4a, however calculated on imaginary frequencies and continued with Padé. For every layer the up-spin (\uparrow) is shown to the left, and the down-spin (\downarrow) is mirrored to the right.

Interacting central layer without Coulomb potential. In the central half-metallic layer, the parameter of the Hubbard interaction is $U_0/D = 0.8$. Figure 3.6 shows the layer and spin resolved spectral function $A_{l\sigma}$ without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$. It is compared to the corresponding non-interacting case $U_0 \equiv 0$ without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$. In fig. 3.6 the non-interacting Green's functions was calculated on Matsubara frequencies and analytically continued. This is done to have comparable results. In the central layer, the spectral function of the majority spin $A_{0\downarrow}(\omega)$ displays a pronounced shoulder at roughly $\omega \approx -0.15$ and two local maxima for lower frequencies ω . Compared to the non-interacting case, the spectral function of the minority spin $A_{0\uparrow}(\omega)$ remains rather unchanged in shape, but is shifted to higher energies ω . This shift is to be expected, as occupying both spin channels costs additional interaction energy for $U_0 \neq 0$; the minority channel ($\sigma = \uparrow$) feels the repulsion of the almost completely filled majority channel ($\sigma = \downarrow$). This is the effect of the Hartree term $U_0 \langle n_{0\downarrow} \rangle$:

$$G_{ll\uparrow}^{-1} \text{Hartree}(\omega) = \omega + (\mu_l - V_l) - \epsilon - U_l \langle n_{l\downarrow} \rangle = G_{0ll\uparrow}^{-1}|_{V_l=0}(\omega - V_l - U_l \langle n_{l\downarrow} \rangle). \quad (3.7)$$

The positive frequency tail of $A_{0\downarrow}$ induces a small decrease in $A_{1\downarrow}$, and consequently determines its position. Beside this little feature, the non-interacting layers $l = 1, 2, \dots, 19$ seem to be unchanged. Small peaks and wiggles near the band-edge appear arbitrarily as artifacts due to the Padé approximation.

Again, we consider the half-metallic layer $l = 0$. In the interacting case, the Hartree term reduces the spectral function of the minority spin $A_{0\uparrow}$ at the Fermi level $\omega = 0$. The spectral function of the majority spin $A_{0\downarrow}(\omega = 0)$ has a larger relative decrease. Thus, the polarization of the spectral function increase eq. (3.6) from the value $P_{A_0} = 0.61$ in the non-interacting case $U_0 \equiv 0$ to $P_{A_0} = 0.85$ in the interacting case $U_0 \neq 0$.

Inclusion of the interlayer Coulomb potential. The interlayer Coulomb interaction is self-consistently included on a mean-field level as Coulomb potential eq. (2.78). The upper half (a) of fig. 3.7 compares the occupation to the case without the potential V_l ; the lower half (b) shows the potential V_l itself. Like in the non-interacting system fig. 3.4a, we have additional net charge in the central layer, which creates a repulsive potential. In the interacting system however, in the layer $l = 0$ the filling of the majority spin $n_{0\downarrow}$ does not decrease with the Coulomb potential; it is almost identical to the case without Coulomb potential. In the central layer, only the occupation of the minority spin $n_{0\uparrow}$ decreases. Figure 3.6 explains this. In comparison to the non-interacting case, there is not much weight of the spectral function $A_{0\downarrow}$ right below the Fermi level $\omega = 0$. Even with the shift by the Coulomb potential, the Fermi level is still in the regime of the positive frequency tail of $A_{0\downarrow}$.

Figure 3.8 shows the spectral functions $A_{l\sigma}$ for the calculations without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$ to the left (a), and including Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$ to the right (b). Beside the shift of the spectral functions $A_{l\sigma}$ with the potential V_l , also a change in their shape is visible in the interacting system. Figure 3.9 collapses the spectral functions $A_{l\sigma}$ by plotting them over $\omega - V_l$. In the central layer $l = 0$, the structure of the spectral function for the down-spin $A_{0\downarrow}$ is less pronounced in the case including Coulomb potential

Figure 3.7: Effect of the Coulomb potential in the interacting case for $U_0/D = 0.8$. The upper half (a) shows the spin resolved filling of the layers $n_{l\sigma}$. Here the dotted lines n_{σ}^0 denote the occupation without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$. The lower half (b) shows the self-consistently calculated Coulomb potential V_l . The parameters of the calculation are given below the axis.

$V_l \neq 0$. The shoulder in the vicinity of $\omega = 0$ is hardly visible. The two local maxima seen for $V_l \equiv 0$ are smeared out. The maximum lower in frequency turns into a shoulder. For the minority spin ($\sigma = \uparrow$) a pseudogap appears at $\omega \approx -0.6$. The adjacent layer $l = 1$ seems to be unchanged within our accuracy.

We consider the polarization of the spectral function P_{A_0} of the central half-metallic layer. In the interacting case $U_0/D = 0.8$, the inclusion of the Coulomb potential V_l mainly changes features below the Fermi level $\omega = 0$. Thus, the polarization is weakly affected by the Coulomb potential V_l . It decreases from the value $P_{A_0} = 0.85$ without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$, to $P_{A_0} = 0.82$ including Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$.

Comparison of different interaction strengths U_0 . The following results for varying interaction strength all include the Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$. Figure 3.10 shows the spin-resolved occupation. The filling of the majority spin n_{\downarrow} stays almost unchanged with the increase of the interaction U_0 . The filling of minority spin n_{\uparrow} however decrease with the increase of U_0 . The increase of the Hartree term $U_0 \langle n_{0\downarrow} \rangle$ with increasing interaction causes this decrease. The upper half of fig. 3.11 (a) shows the net occupation $\Delta n_l = n_{l\uparrow} + n_{l\downarrow} - n^{\text{bulk}}$; the lower half (b) shows the Coulomb potential V_l . The strength of the potential decreases with increasing U_0 . The main contribution to V_l is the net occupation $\Delta n_0 = n_0 - n^{\text{bulk}}$ of the central layer. Thus, the decrease in Δn_0 explains the decrease in the strength of the potential V_l .

Figure 3.8: Effect of the Coulomb potential V_l on the spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ in the interacting case for $U_0/D = 0.8$. The left side (a) shows the layer and spin resolved spectral function without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$; it is identical to the solid lines in fig. 3.8. The right side (b) shows the corresponding spectral function including the Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$. The spectral functions $A_{l\downarrow}$ of the down-spin (\downarrow) are mirrored down.

Figure 3.9: Spin and layer resolved spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ for the central and first layer with and without Coulomb potential V_l . The spectral function is plotted over $\omega - V_l$ to compensate the effect of the rigid shift due to the potential, thus changes in shape become visible. The spectral function labeled $V_l \equiv 0$ is the same as in fig. 3.8a and the spectral function $V_l \neq 0$ is the same as in fig. 3.8b. The spectral function labeled $t = 0$ is for isolated layers and plotted as a reference.

Figure 3.10: Spin resolved occupation for different values of U_0 . The upper graph shows the occupation of the $\sigma = \uparrow$ spin and the lower of the $\sigma = \downarrow$ spin. The horizontal line indicates the bulk occupation $n^{\text{bulk}}/2$.

Figure 3.11: Net occupation $\Delta n_l = n_{l\uparrow} + n_{l\downarrow} - n^{\text{bulk}}$ in the upper plot (a) and Coulomb potential V_l in the lower plot (b) for different values of $U_0/D \in \{0.8, 1.0, 1.2\}$.

Figure 3.12 compares the spectral function $A_{l\sigma}$ for different interaction strengths U_0 for the central layer $l = 0$ and the adjacent layer $l = 1$. In the central layer $l = 0$, the structure of $A_{0\downarrow}$ for the majority spin gets more pronounced with increasing interaction U_0 . Increasing the interaction strength from $U_0/D = 0.8$ to $U_0/D = 1.0$, the low energy shoulder of $U_0/D = 0.8$ turns into a local maximum, and the shoulder close to $\omega = 0$ gets clearly visible. Increasing the interacting strength further to $U_0/D = 1.2$, a three-peaked structure becomes apparent. The two maxima become sharper and the shoulder turns into a third maximum. The local minimum in the spectral function of the minority spin $A_{0\uparrow}$ gets deeper for $U_0/D = 1.0$ compared to $U_0/D = 0.8$. For the setup with $U_0/D = 1.2$, the accuracy is too low to make a statement.

We review the central half-metallic layer. The polarization of the spectral function increases with increasing U_0 . The following table summarizes the polarization of the different cases:

interaction U_0/D	polarization P_{A_0}	
	$V_l \equiv 0$	$V_l \neq 0$
0.0	0.61	0.20
0.8	0.85	0.82
1.0		0.84
1.2		0.86

Figure 3.12: Spin and layer resolved spectral function $A_{l\sigma}(\omega)$ for the central layer $l = 0$ and first layer $l = 1$ for different values of U_0 . The spectral function labeled $t = 0$ is for isolated layers and plotted as a reference.

In our setup, we generate the half-metallicity of the central layer by a magnetic field $h_0/D = -0.9$, while keeping the minority spin $\sigma = \downarrow$ at half filling. The net charge of this layer $\Delta n_0 = n_0 - n^{\text{bulk}}$ generates an interlayer Coulomb potential; the potential shifts the weight of the spectral function of the majority spin $A_{0\downarrow}$ back to the Fermi level. It also shifts the weight of the spectral functions of the minority spin $A_{0\uparrow}$ to higher frequencies ω , reducing the amplitude of $A_{0\uparrow}$ at the Fermi level $\omega = 0$. Thus, the Coulomb potential reduces the polarization in this setup. The interaction U_0 reduces the net charge Δn_0 due to the Hartree term, thus it weakens the Coulomb potential. Furthermore, it shifts the weight of the spectral function of the majority spin $A_{0\downarrow}$ to lower frequencies. Thus, the interacting U_0 increases the polarization.

4. Outlook: Steady-state transmission for heterostructures

We are interested in the transport properties of the systems analyzed in section 3. We have not investigated two-particle properties, we can however readily evaluate the transmission from the one-particle Green's function.

We assume our heterostructure to be embedded into non-interacting semi-infinite leads on both sides. For the leads we take the same structure as the non-interacting part of our heterostructure, this means layers of half-filled Bethe lattices with half-bandwidth $D = 1$ stacked in z -direction, which are coupled by nearest-neighbor hopping $t = 0.2$.

We preliminarily calculate the transmission using [37]

$$T(\omega) = \text{Tr}(\mathbf{\Gamma}^L(\omega)\mathbf{G}^r(\omega)\mathbf{\Gamma}^R(\omega)\mathbf{G}^a(\omega)), \quad (4.1)$$

with the left (right) level-width function

$$\Gamma_{ij}^{L(R)}(\omega) = 2\pi \sum_{n \in L(R)} \rho_n(\epsilon) t_{ni} t_{nj}^*. \quad (4.2)$$

This equation is in general valid for non-interacting models, the application for interacting models requires further justification. Nevertheless, we apply this formula to our system, to get a preliminary perspective. Like in section 2.2, we use the multi-indices $i = (l\alpha)$; the indices l denote layers and α sites within a layer. We write the trace as trace over the layers and over the sites within a layer $\text{Tr} = \text{Tr}_l \text{Tr}_\alpha$. Due to the translational invariance within the layers, we can diagonalize all matrices in the site indices α by the same transformation, a Fourier transform. This yields

$$T(\omega) = \text{Tr}_l \sum_k \mathbf{\Gamma}^L(k, \omega) \mathbf{G}^r(k, \omega) \mathbf{\Gamma}^R(k, \omega) \mathbf{G}^a(k, \omega). \quad (4.3)$$

We replace the k -sum by the integral over the layer DOS

$$T(\omega) = \int d\epsilon \rho(\epsilon) \text{Tr}_l \mathbf{\Gamma}^L(\epsilon, \omega) \mathbf{G}^r(\epsilon, \omega) \mathbf{\Gamma}^R(\epsilon, \omega) \mathbf{G}^a(\epsilon, \omega). \quad (4.4)$$

We only have nearest-neighbor hopping between the layers, so the only non-vanishing elements of $\mathbf{\Gamma}^L$ and $\mathbf{\Gamma}^R$ are

$$\Gamma_{11}^L(\epsilon, \omega) = 2\pi \rho_{\text{lead}}(\epsilon, \omega) |t|^2 \equiv \gamma^L(\epsilon, \omega) \quad (4.5)$$

$$\Gamma_{NN}^R(\epsilon, \omega) = 2\pi \rho_{\text{lead}}(\epsilon, \omega) |t|^2 \equiv \gamma^R(\epsilon, \omega), \quad (4.6)$$

where $l = 1$ is the index of the leftmost and $l = N$ of the rightmost layer of the heterostructure. Thus, the matrix eq. (4.3) simplifies to

$$\begin{aligned} T(\omega) &= \int d\epsilon \rho(\epsilon) \gamma^L(\epsilon, \omega) G_{1N}^r(\epsilon, \omega) \gamma^R(\epsilon, \omega) G_{N1}^a(\epsilon, \omega) \\ &= \int d\epsilon \rho(\epsilon) \gamma^L(\epsilon, \omega) |G_{1N}^r(\epsilon, \omega)|^2 \gamma^R(\epsilon, \omega). \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

Figure 4.1: Transmission for spin $\sigma = \uparrow$ and $\sigma = \downarrow$ with and without Coulomb potential V_l for the systems with $U_0/D = 0$ and $U_0/D = 0.8$. Mind the different scales for the transmission of the up-spin T_\uparrow and the down-spin T_\downarrow . The dotted line is the comparison with the homogeneous system, where all layers are non-interacting and half filled. For the non-interacting system $U_0/D = 0$ the transmission for the $\sigma = \uparrow$ spin $T_\uparrow(\omega)$, is identical to the homogeneous system.

Figure 4.2: Polarization of the transmission with and without Coulomb potential V_l for the systems with $U_0/D = 0$ and $U_0/D = 0.8$.

Figure 4.3: Transmission for $\sigma = \uparrow$ and $\sigma = \downarrow$ with Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$ for different values of U_0 . Mind the different scales for the transmission of the up-spin T_\uparrow and the down-spin T_\downarrow .

Figure 4.4: Polarization of the transmission with Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$ for different values of U_0 .

Figure 4.1 shows the transmission for the non-interacting and the interacting setup with $U_0/D = 0.8$ with and without Coulomb potential. This is the transmission corresponding to the setups studied in figs. 3.4 and 3.8. Figure 4.2 shows the corresponding polarization. Figure 4.3 shows the transmission for the interacting systems for the values $U_0/D \in \{0.8, 1.0, 1.2\}$. Figure 4.2 shows the corresponding polarization. The polarization of the transmission

$$P_T(\omega) = \frac{T_{\uparrow}(\omega) - T_{\downarrow}(\omega)}{T_{\uparrow}(\omega) + T_{\downarrow}(\omega)} \quad (4.8)$$

differs from the polarization of the spectral function P_{A_0} . It is important to investigate transport properties of the half-metallic heterostructures, not just the spectral function.

5. Conclusion

We studied heterostructures with one interacting half-metallic layer in the center, surrounded by non-interacting non-magnetic layers. We modeled the system using an inhomogeneous single-band Hubbard Hamiltonian. We treated the strong electron correlation of the central half-metallic layer within r -DMFT, considering a purely local self-energy. To study electronic charge reconstruction we extended the Hubbard Hamiltonian including long-ranged Coulomb repulsion between the layers. We treated the long-ranged Coulomb interaction on a mean-field level; an electrostatic potential was self-consistently calculated from the Poisson equation. The study of the model is entirely numerical.

We used a magnetic field in form of a Zeeman term to generate the half-metallicity. As a result of the magnetic field, the down-spin is almost completely filled and has little spectral weight at the Fermi level. We investigated the one-particle quantities, the filling, the spectral function, and its spin polarization. The spin polarization of the spectral function is reduced in the half-metallic layer, due to charge transfer with the adjacent non-magnetic layers. In this setup, the net charge of the half-metallic layer creates a Coulomb potential, which decreases the polarization. For a non-interacting half-metallic layer, the polarization is decreased to roughly a third. For an interacting half-metallic layer, this decrease was just a few percent. The combination of long-ranged Coulomb potential and strong local correlation produces a new feature in the spectral function of the metallic minority spin of the half-metallic layer; a pseudogap appeared just below the Fermi level.

We were only able to consider a single half-metallic layer. For a larger region of adjacent half-metallic layers, we faced the sign problem with our impurity solver. An anti-ferromagnetic setup of adjacent half-metallic layers was possible, this setup is, however, not studied in this thesis. We considered an interlayer hopping that is smaller than the in-layer hopping. Increasing the interlayer hopping to the same strength as the in-layer hopping makes the problem numerically harder; it is more difficult to converge the calculations.

As an outlook, we did some preliminary calculations of the transmission. The polarization of the transmission clearly differs from the polarization of the spectral function. Thus, for applications of half-metals such as spin filters, it is important to calculate the conductivity and its polarization in these heterostructures.

Appendices

A. Fermionic field integrals

We will mainly follow the introduction to field integrals of [38], further reference are [22,23].

We will consider the partition function for a normal ordered Hamilton. The goal is to rewrite the trace over the operator $e^{-\beta(\hat{H}-\mu\hat{N})}$ as a field integral without operators. The basic strategy will be to slice the exponential of the Hamilton into small steps. Then we will insert resolutions of identity to project each of those operators into a suitable basis and evaluate the matrix elements. Finally, we will collect the slices again, neglecting higher orders.

The normal ordered Hamilton \hat{H} of interest is

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{ij} h_{ij} \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j + \sum_{ijkl} V_{ijkl} \hat{a}_i^\dagger \hat{a}_j^\dagger \hat{a}_l \hat{a}_k \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with the fermionic creation and annihilation operators \hat{a}_i^\dagger and respectively \hat{a}_i for the state i .¹⁰ The grand canonical partition function \mathcal{Z} reads

$$\mathcal{Z} = \text{Tr} \left(e^{-\beta(\hat{H}-\mu\hat{N})} \right) = \sum_{\{n\}} \langle \{n\} | e^{-\beta(\hat{H}-\mu\hat{N})} | \{n\} \rangle. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

For a more condensed notation we will absorb in the following the chemical potential into the Hamilton by substituting $h_{ij} \rightarrow h_{ij} - \delta_{ij}\mu$.

A.1. Grassmann numbers and the partition function

Coherent states and Grassmann numbers. First we will introduce a suitable basis, the *coherent states*. The coherent states $|\theta\rangle$ are eigenstates of the annihilation operators $\hat{a}_i|\theta\rangle = \theta_i|\theta\rangle$. Evidently the θ_i cannot be complex numbers as they have to anticommute with the operators and themselves $0 = \{\hat{a}_i, \theta_j\} = \{\theta_i, \theta_j\}$. The θ_i are the *Grassmann numbers*, or more specifically the *generators of the Grassmann algebra*. We define them to commute with the vacuum $[\theta_i, |0\rangle] = 0$. Consequently, they will *not* in general commute with other states. Evidently Grassmann numbers are *nilpotent* θ_i^2 , thus functions of Grassmann numbers are affine in every Grassmann number. The functions can be represented as a linear combination of monomials, where maximum degree of a monomial is equal to the number of Grassmann variables. An extensive reference for calculating with Grassmann numbers is [29]. We define the (left) derivative

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_i} \theta_j = \delta_{ij} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

and integration

$$\int d\theta_i \theta_i = 1, \quad \int d\theta_i = 0, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

¹⁰For us the usual case will be that i encodes the lattice site and the spin.

which are formal identical.

We identify $(1 - \theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger)|0\rangle$ as eigenstates of \hat{a}_i :

$$\hat{a}_i(1 - \theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger)|0\rangle = \theta_i|0\rangle = \theta_i(1 - \theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger)|0\rangle. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

We also identify $(1 - \theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger) \equiv \exp(-\theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger)$ as all higher powers of θ_i vanish. It is a Grassmann even function, this means it commutes with other Grassmann numbers. The commutator $[\theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger, \theta_j \hat{a}_j^\dagger]$ vanishes, hence we can treat it like a complex function according to the Baker-Hausdorff formula. As the expression is Grassmann even, we readily obtain the coherent state $\hat{a}_i|\theta\rangle = \theta_i|\theta\rangle$ ¹¹ as product

$$\left[\prod_i (1 - \theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger) \right] |0\rangle = e^{-\sum_i \theta_i \hat{a}_i^\dagger} |0\rangle \equiv |\theta\rangle. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

We define the adjoint state

$$\langle\theta| = \langle 0| e^{\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \hat{a}_i}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

this is the left eigenstate of the creation operators $\langle\theta|\hat{a}_i^\dagger = \langle\theta|\bar{\theta}_i$. The matrix elements are

$$\langle\theta'|\theta\rangle = e^{\sum_i \bar{\theta}'_i \theta_i}, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

the states are neither orthogonal nor normalized. These states build a convenient representation, as they diagonalize normal ordered operators. We now show that they build a complete basis by plugging in the resolution of identity of the Fock states

$$\left[\prod_i \int d\bar{\theta}_i \int d\theta_i \right] e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} |\theta\rangle \langle\theta| = \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \sum_{\{n_i\}} |\{n\}\rangle \langle\{n\}|\theta\rangle \langle\theta|. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Here we introduced the short notation $\int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta)$ for the integrations in square brackets. We first calculate the overlap $\langle\{n\}|\theta\rangle$. We represent $\langle\{n\}|$ in terms of annihilation operators. For a state with N particles we write $\langle\{n\}| = \langle 0| \prod_{i=1}^N \hat{a}_i$. In the overlap the \hat{a}_i act on their eigenstate. We gain no additional sign if we keep the order, as we move every operator past the same number of Grassmann numbers to the right to act on $|\theta\rangle$ as we move them left to their original position. Thus, we get the overlap

$$\langle\{n\}|\theta\rangle = \prod_{i=1}^N \theta_i \langle 0|\theta\rangle = \prod_{i=1}^N \theta_i. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

¹¹This is a shorthand notation $|\theta\rangle \equiv |\{\theta_i\}\rangle$, it is the simultaneous eigenstate of all annihilation operators.

Now we can evaluate the integral

$$\begin{aligned}
\int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \langle \{n\} | \theta \rangle \langle \theta | &= \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \left[\prod_{i=1}^N \theta_i \right] \langle 0 | e^{\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \hat{a}_i} \\
&= \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \langle 0 | \left[\prod_{i=1}^N \theta_i \right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^N (1 + \bar{\theta}_i \hat{a}_i) \right] \\
&= \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_{i>N} \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \langle 0 | \left[\prod_{i=1}^N \theta_i \right] \left[\prod_{i=1}^N \bar{\theta}_i \hat{a}_i \right] \tag{A.11} \\
&= \left[\prod_{i>N} \int d\bar{\theta}_i \int d\theta_i \right] \left[\prod_{i>N} (1 - \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i) \right] \langle 0 | \left[\prod_{i=1}^N \hat{a}_i \right] \\
&= \langle \{n\} |.
\end{aligned}$$

In the first equality we plugged in the overlap (A.10) and expanded the state $\langle \{n\} |$ into its annihilation operators. The integral is finite only if all pairs θ_i and $\bar{\theta}_i$ appear. Hence, all unpaired terms $\bar{\theta}_i \hat{a}_i$ vanish, and we can limit the product coming from the second exponential to $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. In the next step we will also drop the 1 in the factors $(1 + \bar{\theta}_i \hat{a}_i)$, as it only appears in terms with an unpaired θ_i . In the first exponential all terms containing Grassmann numbers with index $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ also vanish, as they would result in higher powers of the Grassmann numbers. Plugging equation (A.11) into (A.9) we obtain the resolution of identity

$$\int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} |\theta\rangle \langle \theta| = \sum_{\{n_i\}} |\{n\}\rangle \langle \{n\}| = \mathbb{1}, \tag{A.12}$$

the coherent states build a complete basis.

Partition function and the field integral. With this basis we can construct the field integral in complete analogy to the path integral, we have to respect the order of terms due to the Grassmann algebra. First we rewrite the partition function \mathcal{Z} eq. (A.2), to take the trace over our new basis. We insert the identity (A.12) into \mathcal{Z}

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \sum_{\{n_i\}} \langle \{n\} | \theta \rangle \langle \theta | e^{-\beta \hat{H}} | \{n\} \rangle. \tag{A.13}$$

To evaluate the sum over $\{n_i\}$ we need to push the overlap $\langle \{n\} | \theta \rangle$ to the right. The integration measure as well as $e^{-\beta \hat{H}}$ are Grassmann even,¹² however not in general the overlap $\langle \theta | \{n\} \rangle$ as we see in eq. (A.10). We have to push N θ_i past N $\bar{\theta}_i$ which yields a factor $-1^{N^2} = -1^N$. We absorb this factor into the exponential function in the state $\langle \theta |$ and get

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_i \bar{\theta}_i \theta_i} \langle -\theta | e^{-\beta \hat{H}} | \theta \rangle. \tag{A.14}$$

¹²This is the case because of the structure of our Hamilton, having always pairs of creation and annihilation operators.

and the inverse relations

$$\theta_i^\ell = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \theta_i^n e^{i\pi n \ell / N} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{\theta}_i^\ell = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \bar{\theta}_i^n e^{-i\pi n \ell / N}. \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Plugging these into S_N we obtain

$$S_N = \delta \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \left[\sum_{ij} \delta^{-1} \bar{\theta}_i^n \theta_j^n (1 - e^{i\pi n / N}) \delta_{ij} + h_{ij} \bar{\theta}_i^n \theta_j^n e^{i\pi n / N} \right] \\ + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n,m,n',m'=0}^{N-1} \sum_{ijkl} V_{ijkl} \bar{\theta}_i^n \bar{\theta}_j^m \theta_k^{n'} \theta_l^{m'} e^{i\pi(n+m)/N} \delta_{n+m,n'+m'} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

For small δ we can use $\delta^{-1}(1 - e^{i\pi n \delta}) = -i\pi n + \mathcal{O}(\delta)$.

Taking the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$ the sum $\delta \sum_n$ turns into an integral. We will call the integration variable τ and interpret as imaginary time going from 0 to β . We promote the θ_i^ℓ to functions of τ with $\theta_i(\tau_\ell) = \theta_i^\ell$ and $\tau_\ell = \ell\delta$, and consequently $\bar{\theta}(0) = -\bar{\theta}(\beta)$. We define the measure of the field integration

$$\int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\theta}, \theta] \equiv \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{\ell=0}^{N-1} \int d(\bar{\theta}^\ell, \theta^\ell), \quad (\text{A.22})$$

and formally introduce $\lim_{\delta \rightarrow 0} \delta^{-1}(\theta^n - \theta^{n-1}) \equiv \partial_\tau \theta(\tau)$. In the following we won't explicitly note the τ -dependence of the Grassmann fields if all fields depend on the same τ . The field integral representation of the partition function (A.2) reads

$$\mathcal{Z} = \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\theta}, \theta] e^{-S[\bar{\theta}, \theta]} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

with the action

$$S[\bar{\theta}, \theta] = \int_0^\beta d\tau [(-\partial_\tau \bar{\theta})\theta + H[\bar{\theta}, \theta]] = \int_0^\beta d\tau [\bar{\theta} \partial_\tau \theta + H[\bar{\theta}, \theta]]. \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Or with the Hamiltonian explicitly written

$$S[\bar{\theta}, \theta] = \int_0^\beta d\tau \left[\sum_{ij} \bar{\theta}_i (\partial_\tau + h_{ij}) \theta_j + \sum_{ijkl} V_{ijkl} \bar{\theta}_i \bar{\theta}_j \theta_l \theta_k \right]. \quad (\text{A.25})$$

The equality $\int d\tau (-\partial_\tau \bar{\theta})\theta = \int d\tau \bar{\theta} \partial_\tau \theta$ is formally identical to an integration by parts. We can verify it by looking at the discrete form, there we just need to change the dummy variables over which we sum. As explicitly calculated in (A.21) we can evaluate the integral by Fourier transformation. With the fermionic Matsubara frequencies $\omega_n = \frac{(2n+1)\pi}{\beta}$, the Fourier transform eq. (A.21) writes in the limit $N \rightarrow \infty$

$$S = \sum_{\omega_n} \sum_{ij} \bar{\theta}_i^n (-i\omega_n \delta_{ij} + h_{ij} e^{i\omega_n 0^+}) \theta_j^n + \sum_{\substack{\omega_n, \omega_{n'} \\ \omega_m, \omega_{m'}}} \sum_{ijkl} V_{ijkl} \bar{\theta}_i^n \bar{\theta}_j^{n'} \theta_k^m \theta_l^{m'} \delta_{n+n', m+m'} e^{i(\omega_n + \omega_m) 0^+}. \quad (\text{A.26})$$

The exponential functions are convergence generating factors, which can be dropped if not needed.

A.2. Green's functions

We briefly introduce the notation of Green's functions in the field integral representation. Expectation values are defined as

$$\langle \cdot \rangle_S = \frac{1}{\mathcal{Z}} \int \mathcal{D}[\bar{\theta}, \theta] \cdot e^{-S[\bar{\theta}, \theta]}. \quad (\text{A.27})$$

The *one-particle* or *two-point* Green's function is then defined

$$G_{ij}(\tau, \tau') = -\langle \theta_i(\tau) \bar{\theta}_j(\tau') \rangle_S \quad (\text{A.28})$$

and the *n-particle* or *2n-point* Green's function as

$$G_{i_1, \dots, i_n; j_1, \dots, j_n}(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n; \tau'_1, \dots, \tau'_n) = -\langle \theta_{i_1}(\tau_1) \dots \theta_{i_n}(\tau_n) \bar{\theta}_{j_1}(\tau'_1) \dots \bar{\theta}_{j_n}(\tau'_n) \rangle_S. \quad (\text{A.29})$$

The Green's can also be generated by differentiation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta^{2n}}{\delta \bar{\eta}_{i_1}(\tau_1) \dots \bar{\eta}_{i_n}(\tau_n) \eta_{j_1}(\tau'_1) \dots \eta_{j_n}(\tau'_n)} \left\langle e^{-\int_0^\beta d\tau \sum_i [\bar{\eta}_i(\tau) \theta_i(\tau) + \bar{\theta}_i(\tau) \eta_i(\tau)]} \right\rangle_S \\ = (-1)^{n+1} \left\langle \theta_{i_1}(\tau_1) \dots \theta_{i_n}(\tau_n) \bar{\theta}_{j_1}(\tau'_1) \dots \bar{\theta}_{j_n}(\tau'_n) \right\rangle_S, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.30})$$

the expectation value $\langle e^{-\int d\tau \sum_i (\bar{\eta}_i \theta_i + \bar{\theta}_i \eta_i)} \rangle$ is called generating function. [22, 23]

For *non-interacting* systems $V_{ijkl} = 0$ the action S_0 is quadratic and expectation values can be explicitly evaluated. The Gaussian integral for Grassmann numbers reads [38]

$$\frac{1}{\det(A_{ij})} \int d(\bar{\theta}, \theta) e^{-\sum_{ij} \bar{\theta}_i A_{ij} \theta_j - \bar{\eta}_i \theta_i - \bar{\theta}_i \eta_i} = e^{\sum_{ij} \bar{\eta}_i (\mathbf{A}^{-1})_{ij} \eta_j}, \quad (\text{A.31})$$

$(\mathbf{A}^{-1})_{ij}$ is the inverse of the matrix A_{ij} . Differentiating both sides of eq. (A.31) with respect to η and $\bar{\eta}$ at $\eta, \bar{\eta} = 0$ we obtain

$$\langle \theta_{i_1} \dots \theta_{i_n} \bar{\theta}_{j_1} \dots \bar{\theta}_{j_n} \rangle_{S_0} = \sum_P (-1)^{N(P)} (\mathbf{A}^{-1})_{i_1 j_{P(1)}} \dots (\mathbf{A}^{-1})_{i_n j_{P(n)}}. \quad (\text{A.32})$$

We sum over all permutations P , $N(P)$ is the number of inversions in P . For the non-interacting action eq. (A.25) we have $A_{ij} = \partial_\tau \delta_{ij} + h_{ij}$. Thus, in frequency representation the non-interacting one-particle Green's function is simply

$$G_{ij}(i\omega_n) = -\langle \theta_i^n \bar{\theta}_j^n \rangle_S = (i\omega_n \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{h})_{ij}^{-1}. \quad (\text{A.33})$$

The *n-particle* Green's functions can then be expressed in terms of permutations of the product of one-particle Green's functions according to eq. (A.32).

B. Matrix manipulation of the cavity Green's function

We derive the connection between the one-particle cavity Green's function $G_{ij}^{(\circ)}$ and the full Green's function G_{ij} . We first derive the relation for a non-interacting system and subsequently discuss that it can be generalized to interacting systems in the limit of infinite coordination number. All Green's functions in the following are spin dependent in general, but we suppress the sigma dependence in the formulas to lighten the notation.

We write the inverse of the full and the cavity Green's function for the *non-interacting* system in matrix form:

$$\mathbf{G}_0^{-1} = i\omega_n \mathbf{1}_{N \times N} + \boldsymbol{\mu} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \mathbf{t} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)-1} = i\omega_n \mathbf{1}_{N-1 \times N-1} + \boldsymbol{\mu}^{(\circ)} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(\circ)} - \mathbf{t}^{(\circ)}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

We introduced the matrix quantities for chemical potential, onsite-energy and hopping $\boldsymbol{\mu} = \text{diag}(\mu_i)$, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \text{diag}(\epsilon_i)$ and $(\mathbf{t})_{ij} = t_{ij}$. The inverse of the cavity Green's function looks the identical to the full Green's function, just one site \circ was removed. Thus, the matrix representations of chemical potential $\boldsymbol{\mu}^{(\circ)}$, on-site energy $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(\circ)}$ and hopping $\mathbf{t}^{(\circ)}$ of the cavity system are identical to those of the lattice with row and column \circ removed. We introduced the short-hand notation $\xi_i = i\omega_n + \mu_i - \epsilon_i$. We relate eqs. (B.1) and (B.2) by interpreting eq. (B.1) as a block matrix:

$$\mathbf{G}_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \xi_{\circ} & -\mathbf{t}_{\circ\cdot} \\ -\mathbf{t}_{\cdot\circ} & \mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

We introduced $\mathbf{t}_{\circ\cdot} = (t_{\circ 1}, \dots)$ and $\mathbf{t}_{\cdot\circ} = (t_{1\circ}, \dots)^\top = \mathbf{t}_{\circ\cdot}^\top$. The inverse of eq. (B.3) is the lattice Green's function, which we write as the block matrix

$$\mathbf{G}_0 = \begin{pmatrix} G_{0\circ\circ} & \mathbf{G}_{0\circ\cdot} \\ \mathbf{G}_{0\cdot\circ} & \mathbf{G}'_0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Using $\mathbf{G}_0^{-1} \mathbf{G}_0 = \mathbf{1}_{N \times N}$ we get the elements

$$\xi_{\circ} G_{0\circ\circ} - \mathbf{t}_{\circ\cdot} \mathbf{G}_{\cdot\circ} = 1 \quad (\text{B.5a})$$

$$\xi_{\circ} \mathbf{G}_{\circ\cdot} - \mathbf{t}_{\circ\cdot} \mathbf{G}'_0 = \mathbf{0}_{1 \times N-1} \quad (\text{B.5b})$$

$$-\mathbf{t}_{\cdot\circ} G_{0\circ\circ} + \mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)-1} \mathbf{G}_{0\cdot\circ} = \mathbf{0}_{N-1 \times 1} \quad (\text{B.5c})$$

$$-\mathbf{t}_{\cdot\circ} \mathbf{G}_{\circ\cdot} + \mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)-1} \mathbf{G}'_0 = \mathbf{1}_{N-1 \times N-1}. \quad (\text{B.5d})$$

We multiply eq. (B.5c) with $\mathbf{G}_{0\cdot\circ}$ from the right and subtract it from eq. (B.5d) multiplied with $G_{0\circ\circ}$:

$$G_{0\circ\circ} \mathbf{1}_{N-1 \times N-1} = \mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)-1} (\mathbf{G}'_0 G_{0\circ\circ} - \mathbf{G}_{0\cdot\circ} \mathbf{G}_{0\cdot\circ}). \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Solving for $\mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)}$ yields the known relation between the cavity Green's function and the full Green's function for the non-interacting system:

$$\mathbf{G}_0^{(\circ)} = \mathbf{G}'_0 - \frac{\mathbf{G}_{0\circ}\mathbf{G}_{\circ 0}}{G_{0\circ\circ}}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

In DMFT the quantity of interest is not an expression for the cavity Green's function itself, but the sum

$$\sum_{ij \neq \circ} t_{oi} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)} t_{j\circ} = \mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}^{(\circ)} \mathbf{t}_\circ. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

This equation can be further simplified by using the other two elements of eq. (B.5) that we did not use so far. We plug the relation between cavity Green's function $G^{(\circ)}$ and full Green's function G eq. (B.7)

$$\mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}^{(\circ)} \mathbf{t}_\circ = \mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}' \mathbf{t}_\circ - \frac{\mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}_{0\circ} \mathbf{G}_{\circ 0} \mathbf{t}_\circ}{G_{0\circ\circ}}. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Next we eliminate \mathbf{G}' using eq. (B.5b)

$$\mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}^{(\circ)} \mathbf{t}_\circ = \xi_\circ \mathbf{G}_{0\circ} \mathbf{t}_\circ - \frac{\mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}_{0\circ} \mathbf{G}_{\circ 0} \mathbf{t}_\circ}{G_{0\circ\circ}}. \quad (\text{B.10})$$

Next we replace the sums $\mathbf{G}_{0\circ} \mathbf{t}_\circ$ using eq. (B.5a)

$$\mathbf{t}_\circ \mathbf{G}^{(\circ)} \mathbf{t}_\circ = \xi_\circ (\xi_\circ G_{0\circ\circ} - 1) - \frac{(\xi G_{0\circ\circ} - 1)(\xi_\circ G_{0\circ\circ} - 1)}{G_{0\circ\circ}}. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

So we arrive at the simple result

$$\sum_{ij \neq \circ} t_{oi} G_{0ij}^{(\circ)} t_{j\circ} = \xi_\circ + G_{0\circ\circ}^{-1} = i\omega_n + \mu_\circ - \epsilon_\circ - G_{0\circ\circ}^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

Thus, we can express eq. (B.8) in terms of only local quantities.

In the limit of *infinite coordination number* $Z \rightarrow \infty$ the relations eqs. (B.7) and (B.12) can be generalized to *interacting* systems. In this limit the self-energy becomes local $\Sigma_{ij}(i\omega_n) \xrightarrow{Z \rightarrow \infty} \Sigma_i(i\omega_n) \delta_{ij}$ [26]. Thus, the matrices $\Sigma(i\omega_n)$ and $\Sigma^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n)$ are diagonal. In the limit of infinite coordination number every site i has infinitely many neighbors, removing one of these neighbors leaves the surrounding of the site i unchanged. Thus, we expect that removing a site also does not change the self-energy of the site i . Consequently, we assume $\Sigma_i = \Sigma^{(\circ)} \forall i \neq \circ$, the cavity self-energy of a site is the same as the self-energy of the site for the full lattice. Using the Dyson equation

$$\mathbf{G}^{-1} = \mathbf{G}_0^{-1} - \Sigma \quad (\text{B.13})$$

the matrix form of the Green's functions eqs. (B.1) and (B.2) writes in the interacting case

$$\mathbf{G}^{-1} = i\omega_n \mathbf{1}_{N \times N} + \boldsymbol{\mu} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \mathbf{t} - \Sigma(i\omega_n) \quad (\text{B.14})$$

$$\mathbf{G}^{(\circ)-1} = i\omega_n \mathbf{1}_{N-1 \times N-1} + \boldsymbol{\mu}^{(\circ)} - \boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(\circ)} - \mathbf{t}^{(\circ)} - \Sigma^{(\circ)}(i\omega_n). \quad (\text{B.15})$$

The interacting Green's functions are formally identical, just the $i\omega_n$ -dependence is shifted $i\omega_n \rightarrow i\omega_n - \Sigma_i(i\omega_n)$. We can repeat the steps from in the non-interacting case, we just have a modified $\xi_o = i\omega_n + \mu_o - \epsilon_o - \Sigma_o(i\omega_n)$. Consequently, the relation eq. (B.7) is also valid for interacting systems in the limit of infinite coordination number:

$$G_{ij}^{(o)} = G_{ij} - \frac{G_{io}G_{oj}}{G_{oo}}. \quad (\text{B.16})$$

The sum eq. (B.12) reads in the interacting case

$$\sum_{ij} t_{oi} G_{ij}^{(o)} t_{jo} = \xi_o - G_{oo}^{-1} = i\omega_n + \mu_o - \epsilon_o - \Sigma_o(i\omega_n) - G_{oo}^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.17})$$

C. Heterostructure size analysis

Our system setup consists of a finite number of layers, thus we get finite size effects. We observe two main effects. First the (non-interacting) Green's function shows kinks, in these points the Green's function is not differentiable. Secondly the Coulomb potential calculated according to section 2.3 depends on the system size. We want to choose the system large enough, so that these effects are negligibly. In the following we check them for the system size of 39 layers, that is used in section 3, to see if the size is sufficiently large.

C.1. Finite size kinks in the non-interacting Green's function

The non-interacting Green's function can be directly obtained by matrix inversion. The matrix inversion yields kinks in the Green's function. The number and strength of these kinks depends on the matrix size and thus on the number of layers. We investigate this effect for the retarded non-interacting Green's function $G_0^r(\omega) = G_0(\omega + i0^+)$, as we can calculate it directly on real frequencies ω . The kinks are points, at which the Green's function is not differentiable. We identify them by looking for local maxima in the absolute of the difference between left and right derivative along the real frequency axis.¹³ Thus, we look for local maxima in the function

$$\left| \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \omega_-} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega_+} \right) G_0^r(\omega) \right|. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

We approximate the left and right derivative with the differential coefficient:

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{h \nearrow 0} \frac{G_0^r(\omega + h) - G_0^r(\omega)}{h} &\simeq \frac{G_0^r(\omega) - G_0^r(\omega - \Delta\omega)}{\Delta\omega} \\ \lim_{h \searrow 0} \frac{G_0^r(\omega + h) - G_0^r(\omega)}{h} &\simeq \frac{G_0^r(\omega + \Delta\omega) - G_0^r(\omega)}{\Delta\omega}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

We divide the ω -interval into 5×10^4 equidistant points. Figure C.1 shows the comparison

¹³This algorithm yields too many kinks due to the finite discretization. To eliminate the spurious kinks we have to analyze if the maxima grow with a finer ω -discretization. This is not done here, as we are not further interested in the exact number of kinks.

Figure C.1: Non-interacting retarded Green's functions $G_{0\downarrow}^r$ for the down-spin. The vertical dashed lines mark the position of kinks in the Green's functions. They are determined by the maxima of eq. (C.1), the equation is plotted in the lower half. Mind the different scales. The left column shows the results for a system consisting of $N = 11$ layers, the right for $N = 39$ layers.

of the Green's function $G_{0\downarrow}^r$ for the down-spin between a reference system with $N = 11$ layers to the left, and the system used in section 3 with $N = 39$ layers $\sigma = \downarrow$ to the right. The right column displays the Green's functions corresponding to the spectral functions in fig. 3.4a. Below the Green's functions, the function eq. (C.1) is plotted. This is a quantitative measure of the relative strength of the kinks. The central half-metallic layer $l = 0$ looks almost identical for both systems. The number of kinks increased with the system size, but both curves figs. C.1a and C.1b look fairly smooth, as the kinks are very weak. The only dominant kinks are the two kinks at $\omega/D \approx -2$ and $\omega/D \approx 0$, which correspond to the band-edges of the layer DOS. Their strength is larger than the maximum shown in the lower part of figs. C.1a and C.1b, thus they are truncated in the graph. The adjacent layer $l = 1$ shows strong kinks in the small system fig. C.1c; for the large system fig. C.1d the curves are already comparably smooth, however the kinks are still visible. The outermost layers of both systems show the same behavior. The kinks in the larger system are roughly half as strong as in the small system.

C.2. System size dependence of the Coulomb potential

The system should also be large enough, that the Coulomb potential vanishes before the system boundary. For a symmetric setup, the potential is forced to vanish at the boundary layer as shown in section 2.3. Figure C.2 shows the potential for the non-interacting setup studied in section 3 and the same setup with only $N = 19$ layers. The curves for both system sizes agree, the maximum relative difference is only 6×10^{-3} . Thus, a system size of $N = 39$ layers is sufficiently large with respect to the Coulomb potential. There are no changes in the Coulomb potential to be expected if we further increase the system size.

D. Parameters of Padé analytical continuation

We use continuous-time quantum Monte Carlo to solve the impurity problem. Thus, we obtain Green's function for imaginary time and by a Fourier transform on Matsubara frequencies. Physical quantities however usual need to be evaluated for real frequencies and times. To obtain the quantities on the real frequency axis we use the Padé analytical continuation. Analytical continuation is however in general an ill-posed problem. For noisy data the Padé analytical continuation produces artifacts. In our simulation we have two main sources of error, the finite convergence to the self-consistent solution of DMFT and the finite accuracy of the Monte Carlo solver.

We perform the Padé according to the algorithm given in the appendix of [36]. Depending on how many Matsubara frequencies we use for Padé, spurious peaks appear and the spectral function gets negative at different points. To reduce this problem we will perform the Padé approximation for a range of numbers of Matsubara frequencies and average over the results similar to [39]. In general, results where the spectral function $A(\omega) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \Im G(\omega + i\epsilon)$ gets negative should be discarded as they are not physical. However, we are not able to avoid these unphysical parts, especially at sharp band-

Figure C.2: The upper half of the figure shows the Coulomb potential V_l for a heterostructure with 19 and one with 39 layers. The large system is the same as in fig. 3.4b. Only the right half of the potential is shown, as the setup is symmetric. The lower half shows the difference of the potential between the two system sizes $\Delta V_l = V_l^{39} - V_l^{19}$ with respect to the maximum potential of the larger system V_0^{39} .

edges. Thus, we define a threshold 10^{-2} , and only discard those continuations where $\min(A(\omega)) < 10^{-2} \max(A(\omega))$. This criterion depends on the points ω , at which we evaluate the spectral function to check it. Consequently, we define a reference range on which we will check for negative values. We choose this to be 1000 equidistant points $\omega \in [-4D, 4D]$, where D is the half-bandwidth of the isolated layers. The standard deviation is taken as error.

We will investigate the same setup as in section 3. We consider a symmetric setup of 39 layers. The central layer is half-metallic, characterized by the chemical potential $\mu/D = 0.45$ with respect to half filling and the magnetic field $h/D = -0.9$. The surrounding layers have $\mu/D = 0.0$ and $h/D = 0.0$. The inter-layer hopping is $t/D = 0.2$, the temperature $T/D = 0.01$.

D.1. Convergence generating factor $i\epsilon$

The retarded Green's functions is shifted infinitesimally into the upper imaginary half-plane. In numerics, we use a finite imaginary shift. The reference for the imaginary shift is the first Matsubara frequency $i\omega_0 = i\frac{2\pi}{\beta} = i2\pi T$, which is in our case $i\omega_0/D = i0.02\pi$. We choose the central interacting layer for the system with $U/D = 0.8$ as the reference system to compare the effect of broadening $i\epsilon$. This layer happens to work relatively well with Padé, we get a range of numbers of Matsubara frequencies for which the spectral function is strictly non-negative, even without any shift $i\epsilon$. Thus, in this analysis we discard all unphysical results. A comparison of different shifts into the imaginary plane is shown in fig. D.1. For a large imaginary shift $i\epsilon$ features are smeared out. Figure D.2 shows the small peak of $A_{\sigma=\downarrow}$ at around $\omega/D \approx 0.95$ in more detail,¹⁴ we see that for shifts with $\epsilon/D \geq 10^{-2}$ the peak is smeared out and no more visible. In the down-spin, the plateau shape of the tail for positive frequencies turns into a steady decrease. For $\epsilon/D = 10^{-3}$ the peak is resolved, the general shape also agrees with the less shifted functions, however deviations are still visible. We choose the broadening $\epsilon/D = 10^{-3}$. As a quantitative measure for the changes due to $i\epsilon$ we use the mean squared error compared to the curve with $i\epsilon = 0$. The error is of the order 10^{-3} for the whole ω -range (see fig. D.1).

D.2. Comparison of the layer resolved one-particle Green's functions

Let us first take a look at the non-interacting case, here we can directly calculate the Green's function on real frequencies. It is also not necessary to solve the impurity problem, consequently our data on the imaginary axis has no statistical noisy due to Monte Carlo. This allows us to check where the Padé approximation will definitely fail, and which features it can in principle reproduce.

¹⁴This feature has a large standard deviation, consequently it is possible that is no physical feature but an artifact of Padé. Indeed, if we allow Green's functions to become unphysical to the threshold 10^{-2} and thus average over more values, the peak disappeared and turns into a shoulder.

Figure D.1: The graphs show $\Im G_{\sigma l=0}(\omega + i\epsilon)$ for a range of different ϵ . The Green's function for spin $\sigma = \uparrow$ has been mirrored into the upper half-plane, and the graphs have been shifted to show all lines. The legend gives the mean squared error Δ with respect to the graph $\epsilon = 0$.

Figure D.2: The graphs show $\Im G_{\sigma l=0}(\omega + i\epsilon)$ for a range of different ϵ . The Green's function for spin $\sigma = \uparrow$ has been mirrored into the upper half-plane. In the right plot the graphs have been shifted, to show all lines. The legend gives the mean squared error Δ with respect to the graph $\epsilon = 0$.

A comparison of Padé and direct calculation is shown in fig. D.3 for the central layers 0 to 3 and the boundary layer 16 to 19. We use eight digits of the result for imaginary

Figure D.3: Imaginary part of the layer Green's functions $-\Im G_{l\sigma}(\omega)$, for the non-interacting system without Coulomb potential. The spin-up Green's function $G_{l\uparrow}$ has been mirrored. The black dashed lines are directly calculated on real frequencies, the solid blue ($-\Im G_{l\uparrow}$) and green lines ($\Im G_{l\downarrow}$) by analytical continuation via Padé.

frequencies. The general shape matches, even the kink at around $\omega = 0$ of $G_{2\downarrow}$ is captured by Padé. Padé cannot properly represent sharp band-edges; this can be seen at the low-energy band-edge for the down-spin $\sigma = \downarrow$ of layer 0. Thus, it is hard to identify tails, like in $G_{1\downarrow}$ for negative ω , from the Padé results. It could also just be an edge smeared out by Padé. Padé also fails to correctly capture the exact flanks of the curve, however around the Fermi energy it is accurate. Sometimes artifacts appear, like the wiggles in layer 2 for $\sigma = \downarrow$ or the peaks in layer 18. The standard deviation is not an error, but it seems to be a useful indicator which features are unphysical. For example for the wiggle in layer 2, the standard deviation is too small compared to the exact result. In fig. D.4 we show the same results, but the self-consistent Coulomb potential is included. We observe the same sources of errors for Padé as in fig. D.3.

Figure D.4: Imaginary part of the layer Green's functions $\Im G_{l\sigma}(\omega)$, for the non-interacting system with Coulomb potential. The spin-up Green's function $\sigma = \uparrow$ has been mirrored. The black dashed lines are directly calculated on real frequencies, the solid blue and green lines by analytical continuation via Padé.

For the interacting case, we have no results to compare to, to evaluate the quality of the Padé analytical continuation. Figures D.5 and D.6 show the single continuations over which we average. If the single Padé continuations agree for a larger range of number of Matsubara points, it is a good indicator that this result is reliable.

Figure D.5: Imaginary part of the Green's function for the central layer $l = 0$ for $U_0/D = 0.8$ without Coulomb potential $V_l \equiv 0$. The left shows analytical continuations for different number of Matsubara points; the right the average of them. The color of the lines on the left indicate the number of the Matsubara points taken into account for the line, as shown by the colorbar. The second colorbar indicates which continuations were discarded; the numbers that are black are kept, white ones are discarded.

Figure D.6: Imaginary part of the Green's function for the central layer $l = 0$ for different values of U_0 including Coulomb potential $V_l \neq 0$. The left shows analytical continuations for different number of Matsubara points; the right the average of them. The color of the lines on the left indicate the number of the Matsubara points taken into account for the line, as shown by the colorbar. The second colorbar indicates which continuations were discarded; the numbers that are black are kept, white ones are discarded.

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